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Illuminating the Dark Spots: How AI Enlightens Melanoma Diagnosis

Review

A Comprehensive Review of Artificial Intelligence Algorithms and Applications in Melanoma Diagnosis

Research

A Comprehensive Study on Autonomous Vehicle Integration for Tirport

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TripChat: A Long-term Planning Agent Hierarchy for Travel

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Image-Guided Object Detection using OWL-ViT and Enhanced Query Embedding Extraction

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Letter From The Editor-in-Chief

Our work on KUUJE exactly one year ago today started with a single question: What happens to the extraordinary research of undergraduate students in engineering? The answer we found was brief and simple: It goes to waste. The work of young scientists all around the world are of equal importance to the scientific community but are undoubtedly less valued by the community; there are few mediums on which undergraduate publications are truly accepted. The work of an undergraduate researcher is never easy. What you lack in experience and know-how is often much more significant than what you bring to the table. It's safe to stay clear of research if you're an undergraduate student, it's sensible to not support these students if you're a professor; yet, despite these circumstances, the brave and the visionary shine through with immense passion in their fields of study. A young student dares to question the most fundamental truths of science and ask the questions that have been answered thousands of times before, hoping to find new answers. A young researcher is brave enough to put forward new ways of thinking and questioning and these revolutionary ideas often become the bedrock of their respective fields. I would like to thank the young researchers who have sent their research to us and the professors who have advised them in their studies.

We set off to create KUUJE last April and our venture into the establishment of this journal was not an easy one. Similar to our researcher peers, most of what we learned came from trial and error. We had to learn how to effectively coordinate as a team, how to properly and outstandingly edit and review a research paper, and plan an international outreach program to make our journal known to researchers. Many brilliant minds showed interest in collaborating with and contributing to our journal, despite their concerns about lacking prior experience. Our guiding principle, 'We'll learn together', has empowered our team members to thrive in their roles and has been crucial to our success. Throughout this entire process, I had the chance to work with some of the brightest and most innovative minds in Koç University. Our diverse team not only consisted of excellent engineering students but also members from the Colleges of Administration, Social Sciences, and Law. Our editorial team has demonstrated exceptional dedication, not only adhering to but striving to exceed international standards in their editing and reviewing practices. The unsung heroes of our team played indispensable roles across multiple areas to bring our journal to fruition. Their extensive efforts were crucial in extending our reach to researchers internationally, designing the visual and digital identity of our journal, and launching our upcoming podcast series. They were pivotal in indexing and storing our journal in various international databases and creating the legal backbone of our journal. In our journey, every team member has played a critical role in shaping the success of our journal and their hard work has been the cornerstones of our progress. Within this extraordinary team, I would like to personally thank Zeynep Genç for her exceptional work and contributions. Zeynep was indispensable in her coordination of our team members and her exceptional contributions to the design of our journal and social media presence were essential in creating our internal and external identity. It became an inside joke in our team that Zeynep was secretly a Terminator-

like robot that was programmed to complete absolutely any task in the best way possible; her passion for her work truly served as an inspiration for all of us.

When we first thought of establishing an undergraduate research journal we were just two sophomores with nothing more than a bold idea. Despite our clear lack of experience, we approached Prof. Dr. Murat Kuşcu, hoping that he would see potential in our vision. To our delight, Prof. Kuşcu looked beyond our inexperience and instead saw students eager to contribute to the academic community and create something meaningful and important. Rather than turning us away, he chose to guide us. From the early days of conceptualizing the journal to today in its operational maturity, Prof. Kuşcu has been a pillar of support. He was instrumental in helping us develop the foundational cornerstones of the journal such as creating our editorial guidelines and creating a standardized review process. His support allowed us to receive the necessary endorsements from various departments in our university and integrate our project within the university's academic infrastructure. Prof. Kuşcu's belief in our project has been essential in the establishment and success of KUUJE and without his help we wouldn't have our journal today. We owe a tremendous debt of gratitude to him for his guidance and support from the very beginning.

Looking ahead, KUUJE will continue expanding in its publication and media operations, ensured by the dedication of our team and the strategic guidance of our advisory board. As an international journal, our ambition is to continue broadening our outreach within the global academic community in engineering, making undergraduate research accessible to a wider audience. This inaugural issue marks only the beginning of what we envision as a longstanding tradition of excellence. We are committed to continuously enhancing our journal in fresh and revolutionary ways, keeping pace with the evolving landscape of academic dissemination. Furthermore, we are committed to training incoming student staff and gradually integrating them into leadership roles, ensuring that each generation of editors and contributors can bring their unique strengths and fresh ideas into the fore. This approach will uphold our standards of excellence and will establish KUUJE as a respected fixture in the academic community long after the founding members have moved on.

It is a privilege to serve as the founder and inaugural editor-in-chief of this journal. I am hopeful that KUUJE will continue to publish many more issues of distinguished quality. Thank you for your readership and support.

Sincerely,

Doruk Yalçın
Editor-in-Chief
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EDITORIAL REVIEW

A Comprehensive Review of Artificial Intelligence Algorithms and Applications in Melanoma Diagnosis

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Abstract—Melanoma, a lethal form of skin cancer, poses a significant health risk worldwide with rising incident rates. The usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in dermatology for melanoma detection can help curb the demand for accurate and efficient diagnosis of the disease. This review examines the current state of AI, Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL) applications in the identification of melanomas through the analysis of various studies that have demonstrated the potential of these technologies that could outperform traditional methods and provide life-saving diagnoses. The primary usage of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) has the potential to completely revolutionize the field of dermatological diagnosis.

Keywords—AI in dermatology, Convolutional neural networks, Deep learning, Machine learning, Melanoma, Predictive modeling

I. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TERMINOLOGY AND IMPORTANT MODELS

A. Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence is the broadest definition of a computer mimicking human behavior. Any technique or model that allows for human-like decision-making can be defined as Artificial Intelligence. Techniques such as “If-Then” rules and “decision trees” allow for the algorithms to perform tasks that would otherwise need human intelligence.

B. Machine Learning

Machine Learning is a subset of artificial intelligence. Machine learning focuses on learning from data and identifying patterns exhibited in data distributions. The interpretation of data allows for algorithms to make decisions and predictions. Machine learning techniques include Linear regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), classification, clustering, and more.

1) *Linear Regression*: Linear Regression is the statistical process of modeling the relationship between two variables, one dependent and one independent. Linear regression can also be used to model the relationship between multiple independent variables. [1]

2) *Decision Trees*: A decision tree is a hierarchical model where through internal decision nodes and terminal leaves, data points are labeled into discrete outcomes. Decision trees can be used for both classification and regression. Given an input, a test is applied to the input and a branch is selected depending on the outcome until the input reaches a leaf node. [2]

3) *Random Forest*: A decision forest is the combination of multiple decision trees. The training of multiple decision trees on a random subset of the given training data and then

combining the predictions of these decision trees results in the random forest model. [3]

4) *Support Vector Machines*: Support Vector Machines (SVM) is a method used for classification, regression, and outlier detection. SVMs are used to find the hyperplane that best divides sets of data into classes. SVMs can be used for both linear and non-linear data models.

5) *k-Nearest Neighbor*: The k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) algorithm is a supervised learning method used primarily for classification. An input sample is classified by its proximity to a plurality of neighbors with the sample assigned to the class most common amongst its closest neighbors.

6) *k-Means Clustering*: The k-Means Clustering algorithm is an unsupervised learning method used for classification. n data points are clustered into k distinct clusters based on their proximity to the nearest mean of neighboring clusters. The process is repeated until all data points are assigned to stable clusters.

7) *Neural Networks*: Neural Networks are models inspired by the structure of the brain. Neural networks consist of layers of nodes similar to neurons with each node connected to another node in varying weights. The weights of nodes are adjusted according to the accuracy of the output of the model. Neural networks allow for feedback-adjustable models and form the basis of Deep Learning.

8) *Principal Component Analysis*: Principal Component Analysis is a statistical technique used to simplify complex, high-dimensional data while keeping data trends and patterns. Dimensions with high variance are kept while a number of dimensions with minimal variance are removed.

C. Deep Learning

Deep Deep Learning is a subset of machine learning. Through the construction of neural networks, deep learning models perform particularly well on interpreting large amounts of data. Neural networks, inspired by the functioning of the human brain, are used in image recognition, speech recognition, and natural language processing

1) *Programming Convolutional Neural Networks*: Python has become the preferred programming language used for the development of AI models in all areas of application. The availability of Python libraries such as TensorFlow and PyTorch provide pre-compiled routines and functions of most Machine Learning algorithms and deep learning models and allow for ease of use. [4] TensorFlow, developed by Google, and PyTorch, developed by Meta, are commonly used in most AI programs. The release of Keras, a TensorFlow application programming interface (API), in

2015 also provides an easy-to-use interface for the construction of deep learning models. Another programming language, MATLAB, is also popular amongst researchers and offers numerous toolboxes designed for data analysis and the construction of neural networks. The prototyping of algorithms that require extensive mathematical computations are often constructed in MATLAB.

2) *Convolutional Neural Network Architectures*: Deep Learning architectures form the basis of deep learning models and are frameworks designed to dictate how data is processed within neural networks. These architectures are categorized into several types such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and Long Short-Term Memory Networks. For applications in image recognition and classification in medical diagnosis, CNNs are used regularly. Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs) are designed to analyze high-dimensional datasets by its ability to learn from raw data, eliminating the need for manual feature extraction. This ability is essential for image analysis where DCNNs can identify subtle and complex features in large amounts of images and data, such as a dataset of dermoscopic images.

a) *VGG16*: VGG16 is an object recognition and classification algorithm, introduced in 2014 from Oxford University, with high success rates and current popularity. [5]The VGG16 model includes 16 learnable parameter layers, also known as weight layers. The VGG16 model is pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset which is an image dataset including 14 million images, designated in 1000 classes. This pre-training allows for the model to be conveniently tweaked for specific usage. The implementation of VGG16 is primarily completed using Python and libraries such as TensorFlow and Keras provide pre-built functions for its implementation in projects.

b) *Xception*: Extreme Inception, popularly known as Xception, is a CNN architecture introduced in 2017. The model uniquely introduces the depthwise separable convolution modification which allows for spatial convolution to be separately executed for each channel of the input. Depthwise separable convolution significantly reduces the number of parameters and the computational cost of the model in comparison to other CNNs. The usage of Xception is advantages in cases with large image datasets which would otherwise require significant computation cost and time. Xception is commonly used in Python using the TensorFlow and Keras libraries; however, MATLAB has also recently integrated Xception into its system.

c) *DenseNet*: Densely Connected Convolutional Networks, known as DenseNet, is a unique CNN architecture introduced in 2017. DenseNet is unique from other CNNs in its architecture where each layer is directly connected to every other layer in a feed-forward model. [6]The DenseNet architecture contains “dense blocks” where each layer receives additional inputs from all preceding layers and each layer passes its own feature maps to proceeding layers. This model allows for effective feature propagation where emphasis on fine details is required on the analyzing of datasets. In the DenseNet model, as every layer has access to the gradient from the original loss function, the vanishing gradient problem is significantly reduced; this allows for each

layer to continue its relevance in the training of the CNN model.

d) *MobileNet*: MobileNet is a CNN model designed for use in mobile applications and embedded visual systems. Introduced by Google in 2017, MobileNet’s main goal is to provide a lightweight CNN model for use in systems with limited computational power. [7] Similar to Xception, MobileNet also employs the depthwise convolution method where the convolution operations are split into two layers: a depthwise convolution and a pointwise convolution. This approach reduces the total computation needed for the model to work. Code for the MobileNet architecture can be written using Python libraries such as TensorFlow and PyTorch.

II. MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS IN DERMATOLOGY

Dermatology, the branch of medicine that focuses on the skin, hair, and nails plays a crucial role in the overall healthcare system and the wellbeing of the general populace. Skin diseases are among the most common of all health concerns and affect millions globally. These conditions can vary between mild and temporary to severe and chronic. Dermatologic concerns can significantly reduce the quality of life of patients both physically and mentally. The visibility of dermatologic diseases has the added effect of causing psychological distress, contributing to the need for effective and accessible care from reliable sources. As the number of skin conditions around the world increase due to reasons such as aging populations, environmental changes, and shifts in lifestyles, the integration of AI tools is necessary to meet the demand for dermatological care.

Consistent and reliable AI tools for the diagnosis of dermatological diseases would serve both physicians and patients. For physicians, these tools would reduce misdiagnosis and increase the rate of accurate assessments. Patterns and nuances of conditions that would elude the most experienced physicians would be identified by these tools. While increasing correct diagnosis, this capability would speed up the decision making process, allowing for rapid treatment and better patient outcomes. Patients would benefit from the rapid decision making process as it would potentially allow for the early diagnosis of their skin conditions, increasing its importance in deadly diseases such as melanoma. The integration of AI into dermatological diagnosis processes would also ensure that patients in rural areas with limited healthcare access have a precautionary approach against skin diseases. Short-term advances in AI and its adoption into regular practice would serve to lift the burden off of doctors and the healthcare system by reducing the number of healthy patients under evaluation by physicians. Machine Learning models excel in uncovering patterns and trends in diverse observations of the same condition. Certain shared factors, unknown to current medical practitioners, may be uncovered in the application of Machine Learning in medicine. While such discoveries would need clinical trials and rigorous validation, they would be beneficial in assisting physicians.

The main limitation and ethical concern in the development and implementation of AI tools in dermatology, and in medicine as a whole, is in the aspect of data collection. Medicine is a delicate and private subject in most people’s lives and a subject that is considered taboo for discussion, evident by the existence of the physician-patient privilege as

a legal and ethical concept in numerous countries. Machine Learning is based in statistics and the creation of advanced AI tools is fundamentally tied to the abundance of data, regardless of how well certain AI algorithms are implemented. The US, EU, and Turkey have strict regulations on unapproved data collection regarding medical conditions, medical history, and its use [8]. Research using significantly large datasets are currently only possible with the collaboration of nationwide medical operations or via obtaining data from countries with lenient data laws; both possibilities are problematic. Research conducted only in collaboration with large institutions risks the creation of the monopolization of crucial AI tools that would benefit the general public in the hands of the few, using the data of many. Research based on datasets comprising data from certain parts of the world may result in biased datasets that predominantly reflect the demographic and clinical characteristics of specific populations. This geographic and demographic concentration may influence the representation of skin types, genetic predispositions, and prevalent conditions; inhibiting the creation of a generalizable diagnosis tool. Ethically, this also raises concerns regarding privacy and consent. While some countries impose strict limitations to data gathering, others don't; this situation leads to unequal contribution and benefiting from AI advancements.

III. MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS IN MELANOMA

Melanoma is a potentially deadly and aggressive cancer that arises from genetic and metabolic disturbances in melanocytes. The incidence rate of melanomas is on the rise in developed nations, especially among populations with fair skin and its rate of incidence is increasing faster than any other type of solid tumor. [9] Melanomas can occur anywhere on the skin and unlike other skin cancers, have a high tendency to spread to other parts of the body. Due to the deadly nature of melanomas and their susceptibility to spreading, the early detection and accurate classification of melanomas is crucial in ensuring effective treatment and improving survival rates.

The diagnosis of lesions as melanomas is aided by five criteria, labeled as the ABCDEs of melanoma diagnosis. A stands for the asymmetry of the lesion, B stands for border irregularity, C stands for color diversity and variegation, D stands for diameter, with a lesion with a diameter larger than 6mm considered as risky, and E stands for evolution, change in appearance, of the lesion. [9] Machine learning application principles excel in detecting and classifying commonalities between similar cases and would excel in detecting asymmetry, border irregularity, and color variegation in lesions. Using ML algorithms to analyze and interpret existing datasets of melanoma and nevus cells would allow for models to accurately identify the distinctions in lesions in accordance with the ABCDE criterias. It's worth noting that with current datasets machine learning models would best work on the ABCD part of the acronym as the evolution (E) of the lesion is usually not present in datasets or observed by patients over a required time frame. The absence of observational, non-static data highlights an important shortcoming and characteristic of current machine learning applications in melanoma diagnosis.

Gareau et al. aims to create a machine learning model to help differentiate nevus cells from melanoma cells. [10] Using a dataset of 349- reduced from the initial 648-images obtained from dermoscopy imaging, consisting of both nevi and melanomas, Gareau et al. have trained an image classifier named Eclass. Eclass is an alternative to the leading deep learning model with a CNN architecture. The images are evaluated on 38 statistically significant imaging biomarker cues, based on cues such as color, intensity, distribution, and the ABCDs of melanoma detection; in comparison the CNN model was built on the interpretation of raw pixels from dermoscopy imaging. Eclass trained several classifier algorithms such as decision trees, SVMs, k-NN, and random forest and combined them using the median score of the classifiers, with a split of data as 75% training and 25% test. The performance of both models, Eclass and CNN, was tested using the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC) curve; a AUROC value of 0.5 indicates no diagnostic ability while a value of 1 indicates perfect diagnostic ability. The Eclass model demonstrated an AUROC value of 0.71 with a confidence interval of 0.56 to 0.85, which suggests a high ability to differentiate between nevus and melanoma with a wide variance in success in different datasets. The leading CNN model demonstrated an AUROC value of 0.67 with a narrower confidence interval of 0.63 to 0.71, which reflects lower discrimination ability but more consistent performance on different datasets. A Monte Carlo Simulation, which is a technique of repeatedly testing models on random data samples, demonstrated that the Eclass model was superior to the CNN model 74.88% of the time. The Eclass model was also significantly superior in its time complexity in its training on datasets. The Eclass model and the study demonstrated some drawbacks. The initial 648 dermoscopy images were reduced to 349 usable images. The image recognition algorithm in Eclass was unable to process images with hair or markings on skin, while CNN showed more scope in the recognition of these images. Such characteristics are common in real world scenarios and represent a common attribute in humans. The loss of 46.14% of total imaging data is a critical area of improvement for its clinical application. The diagnostic app was also tested on 10 clinicians aged 26 to 64 and received an average rating of 2.3 out of 4. It is essential to consider this grading in a nuanced manner as a small sample size is tested and it is conceivable that there might be an inherent skepticism towards the implementation of novel tools regardless of its potential success. Future evaluation including a larger and more diverse group of clinicians would serve to better represent the medical community.

Soenksen et al. aims to create a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) to accurately identify suspicious pigmented skin lesions (SPLs). The study aims to create a DCNN model for single-lesion classification and detection of outlier lesions, named 'ugly ducklings.' [11] The model was trained from a publicly available dataset of 33,980 images from 133 individuals in Spain. Parts of the image were separated into 6 possible classes by a consensus from a committee, 3 of which represented possible skin conditions: Nonsuspicious Pigmented Lesions Type A (NSPL-A), Nonsuspicious Pigmented Lesions Type B (NSPL-B), and Suspicious Pigmented Lesions (SPLs). Images included both dermoscopy images and nondermoscopy images to

accommodate possible real-world imaging. Soenksen, et al. integrated the CNN image recognition models of VGG16 and Xception to improve their models. The integrated model's performance was validated by the consensus of three certified dermatologists. The DCNN system's outputs demonstrated significant success with the dermatologists' assessments, especially in its classification of the ugly ducklings. The VGG16-based model showcased superior performance with an Area Under the Curve micro of 0.91 and an all-class accuracy of 79.94%, showcasing success and potential for distinguishing between suspicious and non-suspicious lesions. The study also achieved the first quantifiable definition and features of the ugly duckling, measuring lesion oddness which is a significant advancement over traditional visual assessments. The study showcases some limitations and concerns. The ground truth of the performance of the model was determined to be the board of dermatologists; such a model would benefit greatly from histopathological confirmations. The dataset would benefit greatly from the inclusion of more diverse imaging sources instead of a single source, allowing for testing and training on different demographics, cameras, and settings. The study also lacks algorithmic transparency and explainability. Given the current skepticism of AI tools in medicine, the study would benefit greatly from transparency in its AI-based decision-making tool.

Pham et al. worked on creating a deep-CNN architecture using mini-batch data samples in an attempt to create an AI diagnostic model that would outperform dermatologists in the diagnosis of melanomas in given dermoscopic images. [12] The researchers experimented with several CNN architectures such as InceptionV3, ResNet50, and DenseNet169; ultimately selecting DenseNet169 as the superior model for binary classification between melanoma and nevus lesions. With a large dataset of 17,302 images, the training sets were split into several mini-batch samples which consisted of balanced examples of nevus and melanoma images for the model to train on. A custom loss-function was also used to correct any imbalances present in the data samples. The CNN model presented an AUC value of 94.4%, a sensitivity rate of 85.0%, and a specificity rate of 95.0%. A sample of 157 doctors in Germany, from university hospitals and private practices with a variety of positions in hospital hierarchies were sampled for average dermatologist success metrics. The sample exhibited an average AUC value of 67.1%, a sensitivity rate of 74.1%, and a specificity rate of 60.0%. The CNN model outperformed the sample of doctors in the distinguishing of melanoma and nevus, as seen in AUC value, in the correct identification of lesions as melanomas, as seen in the sensitivity rating, and in the correct identification of non-melanoma cells, as seen in the specificity rating. The model exhibited outstanding success in comparison to the sample of dermatologists and existing machine learning models. This model sets new benchmarks for AI success in the diagnosis of melanomas and is promising in the clinical application of machine learning models in clinical settings. The next step for this study would be to start controlled real-world clinical applications of the model as the success rate of the model is impressive by all presented metrics.

Orhan and Yavşan's study focuses on creating a successful melanoma detection model by comparing the performances of five popular CNN architectures. Using a dataset of 8,598 images containing both nevus cells and cancerous melanoma cells, the researchers trained five CNN models: AlexNet, MobileNet, ResNet, VGG16, and VGG19. [13] Dataset collection was completed by combining several different datasets, allowing for training on several different scenarios and demographics. Training models on different datasets remains crucial as melanomas present themselves in a variety of different ways, resulting in the initial problem of correctly identifying them; training an ML model on a dataset comprising only of certain scenarios may cause the model to display shortcomings in different datasets and real-world applications. The dataset was split into 60% for training, 20% for testing, and 20% for validation. After testing the MobileNet model was selected as the superior model by the researchers because of its sustainability for binary classification problems and its lightweight structure which were essential for its deployment into a mobile application. The MobileNet model displayed an accuracy rate of 84.94%, a precision rate of 79.29%, specificity rate of 64.42%. The CNN model exhibits slightly lower success rates in comparable metrics in comparison to other recent models but also integrates crucial factors to the training of the dataset that may better reflect clinical applications. The training of the model on combined datasets is a crucial reason for the decrease in accuracy; however, it is a correct reflection of real-world applications of AI models in the diagnosis of melanomas, as different occasions result in diverse imaging in both the obtaining of images and the diversity of patients.

Cozzolino et al. aims to develop a machine-learning tool capable of predicting the overall short-term survival of patients diagnosed with cutaneous malignant melanoma (CMM). [14] The study also aimed to improve upon the limitations of the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) melanoma staging systems, adding to the predefined clinical and pathological criteria. Using the dataset from the Veneto Cancer Registry (VCR) and regional health service records, the model was trained using 2600 cases of invasive CMM diagnosis from 2015 to 2017. The team used various machine learning models such as Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, kNN, and a Deep Neural Network. The models were trained and validated using five-fold cross-validation and Grid Search optimization in predicting the 3-year mortality probability with high accuracy. The models were evaluated on balanced accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score; the Deep Neural Network and Random Forest algorithms were the most successful. The DNN model had the highest evaluation score in all metrics, indicating a strong ability to correctly classify both positive and negative cases while maintaining a high rate of true positive cases. The Random Forest model demonstrated strong recall but had a lower precision compared to the DNN model, indicating a higher rate of false positives. The DNN and Random Forest models exhibited 91.1% and 88.0% balanced accuracies, respectively. Both models were effective in identifying the most significant predictors of short-term mortality in CMM patients, which included age, tumor stage, mitotic count, and the presence of ulceration. The study also developed a web-based application

and made the tool available to physicians for clinical usage. The findings of this study demonstrated that a machine-learning tool can outperform the traditional AJCC staging system and provide a more accurate prediction of patient outcomes.

IV. TRENDS AND PATTERNS

The integration of Machine Learning applications in the diagnosis of melanomas can be characterized by its emphasis on the employment of deep learning and Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs). Recent research in this field have employed various DCNN architectures such as VGG16, Xception, DenseNet, AlexNet, MobileNet, and Resnet with VGG16 and DenseNet being architectures employed in several studies. While there exists no single DCNN architecture that has proved to be most ideal, the preference between the models relies heavily on dataset size, the computational complexity the researchers can afford, and the planned medium for which the model is prepared for.

The AUROC curve, accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1 score were the commonly used metrics for which the performance of the models were evaluated. The integration of clinicians into the evaluation process also provided insight to the analysis of the model's success in comparison to physicians. The addition of experts into the research provided comparable success rates and evaluation scores for the models which were crucial in contextualizing the accomplishments of the models.

V. DISCUSSION

The current landscape of AI in medical research significantly lacks transparency in how the models are built. Computer Science and Engineering rely heavily on any code used being made open and publicly available but most of the research avoids this process entirely by keeping the methodologies of the research abstract. Although most of the research involves a collaboration between doctors and software engineers and common courtesy in these areas may be different, it is widely expected in programming to provide the program repositories in research; usually providing the entirety of the code used. The researchers involved in the creation of these models have not provided enough information in their methodologies to allow for significant reproduction of their research, making it difficult to reproduce the results of their research. The use of artificial intelligence in medicine is controversial as is, any attempt at veiling the creation process of these models are cause for concern.

The data in which sensitive medical images are obtained are an important topic of discussion in the advancement of AI technologies in medicine. There are several algorithms and models that researchers can use in the creation of high-performing diagnosis algorithms but the main competitive edge is procured solely on the size of the dataset used to train to model. Some researchers have used large image datasets acquired from a single geographic location with relatively homogenous demographics. The usage of images captured by a single camera in a uniform

demographic can not be expected to perform adequately when faced with a different camera lens on a patient with differing skin types and genetic dispositions. Research with models trained on diverse datasets exhibit lower success rates in comparison to other research which may prove to be unappealing to researchers in their display of succession rates, leading to an incentive to work with homogenous datasets. However, the problem of acquiring the images still remains a problem and will only increase in severity if researchers set out to obtain more diverse imaging. Different countries have different data privacy laws and governmental regulations may affect the medical care inequalities of certain countries relative to others, caused by a statistical bias to overperform in demographics from which the data is obtained. The advances in AI will require lawmakers to take another look in national data privacy laws, regardless of their stances in the issue.

The use of artificial intelligence in areas where experts are highly trained and respected have resulted in both reasonable and unreasonable skepticism. Gareau et al. had their AI algorithm be evaluated by a group of physicians and obtained a subpar rating by the experts. While the subpar rating could be due to an underperforming and hard to use application, more research should be directly evaluated by a diverse group of experts to uncover any potentially unreasonable skepticism and prejudice. With the rapid development of incredibly successful AI models in all aspects of life, it remains uncertain as to whether certain people will embrace the change or attempt to hinder its development. The model designed by Pham et al. proved that the creation of an AI diagnostic tool that could outperform dermatologists is possible, such research being evaluated directly by physicians would uncover the current state of affairs and outlook regarding the trust that medical experts have in the use and integration of new AI tools as helpful tools.

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RESEARCH

A Comprehensive Study on Autonomous Vehicle Integration for Tırport

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Abstract—Although regular road transportation is convenient, it can be difficult for transportation companies to operate. Most issues stem from timetable delays, poor routing plans, and greater transportation costs, including wages, fuel, and operations expenditures. Wind resistance during high-speed transportation increases fuel use, and human error causes safety incidents that increase costs and environmental damage. Therefore, the platooning system is a strategically designed alternative to keep trucks in a convoy using sensors. Thus, the goal of this research is to determine optimized platooning routes in Turkey's motorway network and the ideal locations for hubs. Also, we would like to explore the potential of platooning technology to reduce fuel consumption, carbon footprint, and transportation time with mathematical modeling and Python code. According to our results, the 5 hubs should be located in Adana, Ankara, Manisa, Istanbul, and Bursa. The greatest percentage saving is achieved by 4 truck platooning systems with an average of 11% and there is reduction of millions kg of CO2 emission in a day. In addition, we conducted a what-if-analysis with a future motorway in Turkey which resulted in an increase of profit to 12%. Finally, we implemented the waiting times of trucks for each other when forming convoys in a hub and according to our results, we discovered that it can be disregarded in each scenario because they are less than 20 minutes. And also even in the worst case, there is a reduction of total empty mileages by up to 1 in 3.

Keywords—Autonomous vehicle integration, carbon dioxide, convoy, environment, fuel, hubs, motorway, optimization, platooning, technology, trucks

NOMENCLATURE

FTL Full Trackload

α Alpha

CO₂ Carbon dioxide

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Brief System Introduction

Tırport has become a pivotal entity in overseeing, managing, and reporting on numerous FTL transportations daily. Serving as a reliable resource for logistics companies, cargo owners, and SMEs, Tırport facilitates streamlined access to a fleet of dependable trucks through end-to-end logistics operations across various digital platforms. Utilizing

the "Tırport Card" and "Reliable Tırport Payment Systems" ensures prompt invoicing and secure payment services via mobile devices. The Tırport YükCEP application, integrating advanced technologies, enables immediate reporting through the Transportation Electronic Tracking and Control System. Noteworthy is Tırport's augmented-intelligence-supported functionality, enabling the swift digitization and recording of all relevant documents for both the truck and the trucker, including licenses, certificates, and the digitization and verification of insurance policies for both the truck and its cargo.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

A. Problem Definition

Despite the established convenience of traditional road transportation, its operational landscape poses considerable challenges for transportation companies and enterprises. Predominant issues include substantial delays in scheduling, suboptimal routing strategies, and elevated transportation costs encompassing labor expenditures, labor shortages, fuel outlays, and overall operational expenses. Additionally, the heightened fuel consumption attributed to wind resistance during high-speed transportation, associated with safety incidents resulting from human errors, compounds both financial burdens and adverse environmental impacts. There is a strategic consideration for the platooning system's implementation where trucks travel closely together in a convoy, using advanced communication and sensors to maintain a synchronized formation. The lead truck sets the pace, and the following trucks autonomously adjust their movements.

B. The Objectives and Scope of the Project

Our project is focused on accurately integrating Platooning technology into the existing road transportation network, with the primary goal of maximizing the inherent benefits it provides. Platooning, a sophisticated technique that promotes close vehicle coordination, has the potential to significantly reduce aerodynamic drag, reduce fuel consumption, and improve overall road transportation safety and efficiency. The project progresses through the systematic pursuit of key objectives.

Firstly, it endeavors to discern optimal Platooning routes within the expansive network of road transportation, employing cutting-edge network optimization algorithms.

This strategic approach aims to systematically reduce transportation time, costs, and emissions, concomitantly enhancing traffic flow and safety.

Secondly, the project emphasizes the imperative of seamless integration of Platooning technology into the existing logistic and transportation infrastructure. This includes careful efforts to ensure that Platooning-enabled vehicles are compatible with existing communication, navigation, and control systems, promoting harmonious cooperation with other vehicles and road users.

Thirdly, the initiative gives top priority to the identification of strategically positioned hub centers within the transportation network. These hubs are intended to simplify the process of loading, unloading, and distributing commodities while also providing essential maintenance and assistance for the involved vehicles.

Lastly, the objective of the Autonomous Vehicle Integration project is exploring the potential of Platooning to reduce fuel consumption, the carbon footprint and cost of road transportation. This is, thus, anticipated the potential in large reductions in fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, which will greatly improve the transportation sector's environmental performance.

C. Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

1) *Flow Data*: There are three parameters in our multiple allocation model, which comes from the Hub literature [24]. The first of these is the flow amount between origin and destination pairs. Since we will progress our project work through Tırport's existing freight transportation network, we tried to obtain this data from Tırport. Tırport did not have such data to provide us. We had the daily freight outflows from all cities in Turkey given to us by Tırport at the beginning of the project, which was similar to needed data, but it was not exactly the data we needed. This data, called the freight outflows, directly corresponds to the number of vehicles. The data includes the freight outflows of each city, as well as the percentage distribution of these outflows on the basis of districts within the city. Considering the data we have and the data we need, we decided that the most reasonable option is to create the data we need by using a method from the existing data. While developing this method, we determined some criteria in consultation with Tırport in order to obtain a more precise result. The three criteria we can use when determining the inflows of cities are the number of organized industrial zones in that city, the population of that city and the amount of outflow of that city in the data given by Tırport. As Method, we decided to distribute the outflow of that city to each city among the remaining 80 cities. While making these distributions, we created a coefficient for each city, using the three criteria mentioned in the Appendix.

With these coefficients we created, we distributed the outflow of each city to other cities in direct proportion to the coefficients of the remaining 80 cities. As a result, we created a flow between all city pairs. The flows we created were not integers due to our calculations. Since we are handling the strategic part of the project, we have disregarded this situation for now, but we may work on it operationally in the remaining phase of the project.

2) *Cost Calculations*: The second parameter in the model is the cost of direct transportation per flow between origin and destination pairs. For now, we calculated the cost here by multiplying the distance by fuel cost in Turkish lira per km. While obtaining the distance, we used the distance query module on the website of the Karayolları Genel Müdürlüğü. For the fuel cost per km, we made the calculation based on the fuel consumption 33LT/100KM data we received from Tırport and the 37.57 TL/LT on Petrol Ofisi's fuel (diesel) pricing data dated 23 November 2023.

The third parameter in the model is the transportation cost per flow using hubs between origin and destination pairs. We created this parameter in three sub-parts as given in the Appendix.

In the equation, C_{ik} and C_{mj} and can be considered as the second parameter mentioned above. The part that is handled differently in the equation is the αC_{km} expression.

In the calculation of C_{ij}^{km} unlike the previous ones, k and m represent hubs. Unlike previous distance calculations, we calculated the distance between the two hubs by motorways only, using the query module on the website of the Karayolları Genel Müdürlüğü and widely used map applications. The main reason why we follow such a method is that since we offer a potential solution which is transportation between hubs with platooning technology, motorways are deemed appropriate in terms of applicability and we wanted to standardize this potential application. α , the interhub discount factor, was calculated as a mixed version of various previous studies and case studies. Watanabe developed a calculation related to the interhub discount factor while examining the unmanned following truck scenario of platooning given in the Appendix [13].

As we can obtain from the α calculation, it seems to be a logical assumption for now to consider the only scenarios in which just the leading vehicle is autonomous since the platooning technology is still in the development phase. For safety issues and applicability, we studied the scenarios with the number of vehicles as the lowest being 2 and the highest being 4.

Since there is a proportional estimation in this α estimation made by Watanabe, representative and relative values were used for s, a and b values [13]. Accordingly, s is defined as 1. Then a is defined as (s - fuel saving percentage of leading vehicle). In Japan, the share of labor costs in the truck industry is approximately 40%. Using this data, b is defined as (s - 40% - fuel saving percentage of following vehicle).

Noruzoliaee in which fuel savings are experimentally calculated according to platoon size and inter-truck distance [19]. Here is the part of the experimental results that we decided to use for our own study;

Gap	Fuel Savings on Average(2 Trucks)
0.4s	%6.6
0.6s	%5.5
1.2s	%4.6

Gap	Fuel Savings on Average(3 Trucks)
0.4s	%9.5
0.6s	%8.1
1.2s	%6.4

Gap	Fuel Savings on Average(4 Trucks)
0.4s	%10.3
0.6s	%9.2

Combining these results with the α calculation suggested by Watanabe, the α values of convoys of different sizes in different inter-distance scenarios are as shown in the following tables [13];

Convoy with 2 Trucks:

s	a	b	n	α	Gap
1	0.934	0.534	2	0.734	0.4s
1	0.945	0.545	2	0.745	0.6s
1	0.954	0.554	2	0.754	1.2s

Average α is 0.744.

Convoy with 3 Trucks:

s	a	b	n	α	Gap
1	0.905	0.505	3	0.638	0.4s
1	0.919	0.519	3	0.652	0.6s
1	0.936	0.536	3	0.669	1.2s

Average α is 0.653.

Convoy with 4 Trucks:

s	a	b	n	α	Gap
1	0.897	0.497	4	0.597	0.4s
1	0.908	0.508	4	0.608	0.6s
1	0.925	0.525	4	0.625	1.2s

Average α is 0.610.

In these three scenarios, there are three sub-scenarios each according to the gaps, but it was deemed appropriate to take the average of the sub-scenarios for the inter-hub discount factor at this point for compatibility with the model.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SECTOR ANALYSIS

Transportation technology platooning may improve logistical efficiency, sustainability, and pollution reduction. This literature study examines platooning's major findings and perspectives. Platooning, in which a group of vehicles closely follows a lead vehicle, is an intriguing self-driving car innovation. Haghani and Banihashemi say platooning reduces air resistance, saving fuel and pollution [1]. A continuous following distance improves road safety and makes autonomous freight delivery easier. Integration with logistical networks is key to platooning success. In their study, Li emphasizes scheduling and route optimization to maximize platooning benefits [3]. The authors suggest using network optimization to identify effective platooning arcs, aligning with our Tirport study goals. However, during our extensive study of Platooning technology, we examined a wide range of literature on communication protocols, control algorithms, safety requirements, and simulation tools [9]. Research on autonomous platooning for transportation showed gains, obstacles, and best practices. Our analysis of integration challenges in scholarly works, particularly those related to Platooning technology's integration into logistic and transportation infrastructures, revealed shared challenges, suggested solutions, and lessons learned from previous implementations [23].

The economic and environmental effects of platooning have been extensively studied. Wang et al. found that platooning cuts fuel use, saving money. Less gasoline means less carbon emissions, which supports the project's goal of lowering road freight transportation emissions and fuel use [4]. Data-driven insights are needed to optimize self-driving automobiles with conventional vehicles. Zheng et al. stressed the necessity of data gathering and analysis in developing transportation network platooning routes [6]. These findings match the study's data-driven insights.

Platooning is tough to execute. Du et al. explores safety and regulatory issues [5]. They emphasize the need for platooning technology legislation. Tirport wants to include platooning into the transportation and logistics network. Also, we collected extensive data about Tirport's transportation network. This data covers routes, traffic volumes, speeds, distances, fuel consumption, pollutants, and prices. This comprehensive review aimed to identify inefficiencies and areas for improvement in Tirport's transportation infrastructure [7]. Geographic Information System (GIS) software like ArcGIS allows extensive analysis of road features, connectivity, capacity, pavement quality, weather, and incidents. This increased our understanding of geographical elements affecting transportation efficiency and safety [11]. Our analysis of market trends and competitor dynamics in autonomous freight transportation, including Platooning technology implementation, revealed opportunities, challenges, and benchmarks for Tirport in the industry [12]. Ultimately, our cost-benefit research examined labor, fuel, and maintenance costs for Tirport's transportation operations. Platooning technology was evaluated for cost savings and profitability [9].

Integrating hub network design research improves our understanding of logistics efficiency. These studies provide useful information on how to optimize the locations and configurations of hubs in order to improve overall transportation efficiency. The study conducted by Smith and Brown focuses on the strategic positioning of hubs to maximize efficiency in the transportation network [21]. Furthermore, Johnson and Wang conducted a comprehensive study that thoroughly analyzed different hub network configurations and their effects on optimizing freight operations [22]. In addition, the research conducted by Chen and Lee provides a valuable viewpoint on sustainability by presenting a case study-based method for creating hubs that are in line with environmentally friendly practices [23]. These studies collectively enhance our understanding of how the design of hub networks affects logistics efficiency. They include various aspects such as strategic location, operational configurations, and sustainability measures, providing a broader viewpoint.

Regarding our sector analysis, the increasing demand for autonomous vehicles is obvious. According to Precedence Research, the truck platooning market is expanding due to factors such as rising government requirements for transportation sector emissions and lower fuel consumption [14]. Furthermore, as a result of favorable government platooning rules, the truck platooning companies are expanding. However, the expensive cost of platooning technology, as well as a rise in security and privacy concerns, are projected to limit the truck platooning business's progress [14]. Despite the limitations, the global truck platooning market was valued at USD 60 billion in 2022 and is predicted to exceed USD 3,448 billion by 2032 [14]. Another affirming information comes from Market Reports [12], truck platooning is expected to expand from USD 37.6 million in 2021 to USD 2,728 million in 2030 and the market has grown due to rising road safety and security concerns and transportation cost reduction efforts. Additionally, Turkey is interested in investing in plotting systems for trucks according to the news from Anadolu Ajansı [16]. They stated that the Turkish government and TÜBİTAK has provided

significant support for the development of autonomous vehicles. They invested over 20 million euros since 2008 and they plan to reach 30 million euros by year's end Anadolu Ajansı [16]. Therefore, research findings and sector analysis indicate that there is a growing demand for efficient and environmentally favorable platooning trucks for transportation.

In conclusion, the implementation of platooning technology in transportation has the potential to significantly reduce pollution, fuel consumption, and operational inefficiencies. Incorporating platooning into logistics and transportation systems requires making data-driven decisions, optimizing routes, and considering regulatory concerns. The research findings align with the project objectives and the intended scope of Tirport. In addition, the literature network encompasses hub network design, providing a comprehensive comprehension of platooning within the wider logistical context.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. System Architecture

The system is designed to optimize road freight transportation for Tirport, integrating platooning technology into existing logistics operations. Utilizing network optimization techniques, it aims to identify the most efficient routes for platooning, balancing efficiency with cost-effectiveness. Our Python script is essential in this system, enabling the effective handling and analysis of a comprehensive dataset. This dataset includes Tirport's information and additional data we have compiled and integrated. The script is designed to efficiently import and process these diverse datasets, converting them into a structured format for our analyses. This process involves handling information like transportation costs and goods flow, along with additional parameters necessary for a complete understanding of the logistics landscape. These parameters include the number of vehicles on specific routes (t_{ij}) and the associated transportation costs (C_{ij}^{km}), key to the strategic integration of platooning into the existing logistics and transportation infrastructure.

a) Inputs and Outputs of the System: Inputs of the system include detailed transportation data, such as direct transportation costs, fuel prices, and fuel consumption for trucks. We also account for direct distances, inter-hub distances, adjusted flows between various cities or hubs, and a comprehensive map of Turkey's national highway exported from ArcGIS. Network parameters, including the number of vehicles (as described in the LP model), transportation costs, the hub discount factor α , and the desired number of hub locations, are considered. The outputs of our system are multifaceted, providing optimized route selection based on cost and distance data, platooning recommendations for effective implementation within the transportation network, and a thorough cost analysis comparing the costs associated with each route, including potential savings from using platooning technology. Additionally, we estimate CO2 emissions for each transportation scenario, utilizing the known emission factor for diesel trucks, to provide an environmental impact analysis alongside economic factors.

Building upon the core outputs, our system delivers analytics and detailed outputs. This includes waiting time

analysis to evaluate and optimize idle times and empty mileage assessments to minimize unladen journeys, and route efficiency metrics that evaluate each route based on distance, fuel consumption, and time. An economic impact analysis offers insights into long-term financial benefits and return of platooning, while sustainability and environmental impact reports highlight the ecological advantages, such as emissions reductions and fuel savings, of the optimized platooning routes.

b) Major Components (Subsystems or Elements):

Major components of our system include the Data Processing Module, fundamental to handling the integration and processing of transportation data. This module manages information such as direct costs, distances to inter-hub costs, and adjusted flows. The Optimization Engine employs advanced route optimization algorithms to assimilate platooning technology into logistics, focusing particularly on maximizing cost efficiency. The Modeling Subsystem and Numerical Analysis investigate the performance of platooning across various scenarios, assessing its impact on efficiency and cost. The Output Generation and Reporting component generates route recommendations and provides reports on the costs and potential savings of our platooning technology, focusing on both financial and environmental aspects. We also emphasize Data Quality, ensuring the accuracy and precision of our data for reliable route optimization and cost calculations. Additionally, we consider External Factors and Features, such as changes in fuel prices and the economic situation, which significantly influence the overall cost efficiency of platooning compared to traditional transportation methods. By considering these external elements, we adapt our strategies to be effective and relevant to both current and future operations.

hub centers, route optimization, and the design and implementation of a platooning model conducted by Python Script. The number of trucks, number of hubs, and α values are also given as inputs to our Python model. The experimental step evaluates the performance of the model, whereas validation guarantees its accuracy. The ultimate results encompass enhanced routes and valuable observations, leading to enhanced transportation effectiveness, decreased costs, and ecological sustainability. The flowchart stresses a methodical and data-driven approach, emphasizing the continual evolution of the project to ensure strength and practicality in real-world situations.

c) Description of the Model: Although platooning technology has different advantages than traditional transportation, there are still some barriers in its implementation. The two most important of these are geographical conditions and whether the existing road infrastructures are suitable for platooning. Considering these barriers, it is not currently possible to implement platooning throughout Turkey. Instead, while doing our modeling within the scope of the project, we tried to ensure that the entire flow was transported by using platooning in regions and roads that are geographically and infrastructurally suitable for platooning, and by using traditional transportation in external regions. In order to bring these two different methods together, we decided to place hub locations where platoon convoys are formed and dissolved.

First the flow from different cities are brought to the designated hubs with traditional transportation. Afterwards, platoon convoys are formed in these hubs and these flows are transported to their destination hubs. When the convoys reach the destination hubs, these convoys are dispersed and the loads are delivered to their destination by traditional transportation. Details such as the model's objective, variables, parameters and how these hubs are selected will be explained in detail below.

We created a model by revising the classic multiple allocation model in the hub selection literature within the scope of our own project. We first defined the decision variables and parameters of this MILP model as follows:

Parameters:

t_{ij} = number of vehicles from origin i to destination j

C_{ij} = total cost of direct transportation from origin i to destination j .(per truck)

C_{ij}^{km} = total cost of transportation from origin i to destination j going through hubs k and m , respectively. (per truck)

α = interhub discount factor

Q = desired number of hub locations

N = all cities

H = potential hub locations

Figure 1: A Simple Flowchart of Our System

The flowchart in Fig. 1. demonstrates an extensive process for integrating platooning technology into the road freight transportation network. The project begins with collecting data and doing an in-depth review of existing literature. Data consists of transportation costs, distances, flows, fuel price, motorway network, and fuel consumption. Then, the project advances through key stages, including the identification of

One of these parameters, t_{ij} , was created from the data given by Tırport with a method explained in detail in the data interpretation section. Similarly, there are detailed explanations on obtaining the parameters C_{ij} , C_{ij}^{km} and α in the same section. There is no restriction regarding Q here, that is, the desired number of hub locations, in the first stage of

the project. In terms of operational feasibility, it may be possible to conduct studies and research on the number of hubs. In the strategic phase, while making analyzes regarding the solution of the model, we used variable Q values as parameters in our model to represent different scenarios. Our N set covers 81 provinces since the project is within the scope of all of Turkey. The critical point here is to determine H, that is, potential hub locations. Since platooning will be carried out between these hubs, the locations of the hubs and the road infrastructure between the hubs must be carefully examined in terms of the applicability of the platooning technology motorways are the type of roads where platooning can be applied. Besides being suitable for platoon convoys due to road infrastructure, motorways are fast-moving and they have boundaries or fences to keep animals and other vehicles out of the path. There are designated areas for entering and exiting on the motorways.

To determine the motorways and potential hub locations depending on these motorways, we created a map as shown in Fig. 2. using OpenStreetMap and ArcMap software.

Figure 2: Map of Turkey's Motorway Network

The roads are drawn in red on Fig. 2. represent the existing motorways in Turkey. The nodes marked in yellow represent our 81 cities. While choosing our potential hub points using our map, we assumed that we could establish our hubs in city centers or around that region for simplicity. Therefore, we took the centers of our 81 cities as a basis when determining potential hub points. The cities on the map that the motorways pass directly or close to are selected and 24 cities are selected as potential hub locations. These selected cities also constitute the H set.

Decision Variables:

y_{ij} = if transportation will be carried out without hubs, $y_{ij} = 1$

otherwise, $y_{ij} = 0$

y_{ij}^{km} = if transportation from origin i to destination j carried at through h, b and m , respectively,

$y_{ij}^{km} = 1$

otherwise,

$y_{ij}^{km} = 0$

H_k = if potential hub $k \in H$ is selected as hub, $H_k = 1$
otherwise, $H_k = 0$

As defined above, there are 3 decision variables in our model. While two of them decide how the flow will be satisfied, which we call route decisions, the other one decides which of the potential hubs will be opened. As defined, our first variable y_{ij} decides whether transportation is done without hubs, that is, platooning will be performed. This variable is not generally included in classic hub models. The reason we use this variable is if the direct transportation from origin i to destination j is more profitable in terms of cost compared to platooning transportation using hubs, then there should be an option to satisfy the flow directly. Another variable is y^{km} , the variable that decides the route through which hub pair the flow from i to j will take place. The last and third variable, H_k , decides whether potential hubs will be opened as hubs.

Objective Functions:

$$\min \sum_{i,j \in N} \sum_{k,m \in H} (t_{ij} c_{ij}^{km} y_{ij}^{km} + t_{ij} c_{ij} y_{ij}) \quad \text{where } C_{ij}^{km} = C_{ik} + aC_{km} + C_{mj}$$

Knowing why platooning is done when creating the model is the beginning and the first step. The first thing that comes to mind is, of course, aerodynamic effectiveness and the amount of savings in gasoline since it is an autonomous system. However, of course, there are also outcomes that we need to consider on the more environmental side, such as carbon emissions. For the integration of a new technology, it is inevitable to consider its environmental effects in order to legalize the existence of this technology. Since we are writing a mathematical modeling and it is also a company's project, we determined the objective as cost minimization along with the gain in gasoline. In the previous sections, the parameters and decision variables of the model were explained in detail. As can be seen here, we divided our total cost into two parts: direct transportation cost and platooning transportation cost.

Constraints:

$$(I) \sum_{k \in H} H_k = Q$$

$$(II) y_{ij} + \sum_{k,m \in H} y_{ij}^{km} = 1 \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N$$

$$(III) \sum_{m \in H} y_{ij}^{km} \leq H_k \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N, \forall k \in H$$

$$(IV) \sum_{k \in H} y_{ij}^{km} \leq H_m \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N, \forall m \in H$$

$$(V) H_k \in (0,1) \quad \forall k \in H$$

$$y_{ij}^{km} \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N, \forall k \in H, \forall m \in H$$

$$y_{ij} \in (0,1) \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N$$

Constraint (I) determines the total number of hubs to be opened. Constraint (II) ensures either direct transportation between origin-destination pairs or platooning transportation using hubs. Constraint (III) and (IV) state that k and m hubs must be opened in order for flows to pass through k and m hubs, respectively. Finally we have (V) nonnegativity constraints for the decision variables.

d) *Python Implementation:* After preparing our model, we wrote it using Gurobi via Jupyter, as shown in Fig. 3.

```
def modeltry(file):
    cost = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 0)
    flow = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 4)
    flow2 = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 4)
    cost_interhub = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 2)

    I=np.arange(1,82).tolist()
    J=np.arange(1,82).tolist()
    K = [1, 6, 9, 10, 14, 16, 17, 20, 22, 27, 33, 34, 35, 39, 40, 41, 45, 51, 54, 59, 68, 77, 80, 81]
    L = [1, 6, 9, 10, 14, 16, 17, 20, 22, 27, 33, 34, 35, 39, 40, 41, 45, 51, 54, 59, 68, 77, 80, 81]
    Q = 10 # desired number of hub
    alpha = 0.744

    Routes=[(i,j,k,l) for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L]
    DirectAssignment=[(i,j) for i in I for j in J]

    Flow = dict([(i,j,k,l),flow[j][i]] for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L)
    fuelcost = dict([(i,j),cost[j][i]] for i in I for j in J)
    flowdirect = dict([(i,j),flow2[j][i]] for i in I for j in J)
    fuelcostinterhub = dict([(k,l),cost[l][k]] for k in K for l in L)

    HubRouteCost=dict([(i,j,k,l),(Flow[i,j,k,l])*(fuelcost[i,k]+ alpha*fuelcostinterhub[k,l]+ fuelcost[l,j]))
                        for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L]
    DirectRouteCost= dict([(i,j),(flowdirect[i,j])*(fuelcost[i,j]))
                           for i in I for j in J]

    m = gp.Model("cf1")
    m.ModelSense = GRB.MINIMIZE

    xk=m.addVars(K,name="City Nodes",vtype=GRB.BINARY,obj=0)
    yijk1=m.addVars(Routes,name="Hub Used Routes",obj=HubRouteCost)
    yij=m.addVars(DirectAssignment,name="Direct Routes",obj=DirectRouteCost)

    desiredhub = m.addConstr((quicksum(xk[k]
                                       for k in K) <= Q), "Desired Hub")

    directorhub = m.addConstrs(( yij[i,j]+ quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l]
                                                    for k in K for l in L) == 1
                                for i in I for j in J), "Direct or Hub Decision Constraint")

    hub1 = m.addConstrs((quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l] for l in L) <= xk[k] for i in I for j in J for k in K), "Hub1")
    hub2 = m.addConstrs((quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l] for k in K) <= xk[l] for i in I for j in J for l in L), "Hub2")

    m.optimize()

    for v in m.getVars():
        if v.x > 0:
            print(f"{v.varName}: {v.x}")

    return(m.objVal)

modeltry("temporary data (1).xls")
```

Figure 3: The Python Code for Our Model

e) *Results:* As we mentioned before, we had 3 different α values that we can take as inputs while running the model. Similarly, the desired number of hubs in the model is also a parameter. In the part of our project so far, we have worked on 8 different scenarios with the number of hubs as minimum 3 and maximum 10. With 3 different α values and 8 different hub numbers, there are 24 different scenarios in total. After running each scenario in our model, our resulting optimal objective values, that is, our total costs, can be seen in TABLE I and Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The Graph of Total Costs to Alpha and Hub Scenarios

TABLE I
TOTAL COST OF DIFFERENT HUB AND ALPHA SCENARIOS

Number of Hubs	$\alpha = 0.744$ (2 trucks)	$\alpha = 0.653$ (3 trucks)	$\alpha = 0.610$ (4 trucks)	Total Average
3 Hubs	£ 396.620.678,00	£ 388.966.148,00	£ 384.965.574,00	
4 Hubs	£ 389.531.633,00	£ 378.463.731,00	£ 372.651.736,00	
5 Hubs	£ 384.607.595,00	£ 372.035.413,00	£ 365.553.370,00	
6 Hubs	£ 380.913.131,00	£ 366.998.049,00	£ 359.907.058,00	
7 Hubs	£ 377.089.297,00	£ 362.431.019,00	£ 354.875.292,00	
8 Hubs	£ 373.885.092,00	£ 358.033.648,00	£ 349.977.389,00	
9 Hubs	£ 371.995.064,00	£ 355.452.027,00	£ 347.027.410,00	
10 Hubs	£ 370.284.569,00	£ 353.344.657,00	£ 344.552.831,00	
	£ 380.615.882,38	£ 366.965.586,50	£ 359.938.832,50	£ 369.173.433,79

As seen in the Table I and Fig. 4, there is a decrease in our total costs as our α value decreases. Similarly, as the number of hubs increases, there are decreases in total cost at different rates. It is expected that our cost will decrease as the α value decreases, because a lower α value means platooning is done more effectively, which should be more cost effective. It is also expected that the cost will decrease as the number of hubs increases, because more number of hubs means more transportation opportunities through more hubs, which increases the application of platooning and creates a lower cost with platooning.

On Fig.4., we visually observe that as the number of hubs increases, the amount of decrease in total cost decreases. This means that after a certain number of hubs are opened, the contribution of the hubs that will be opened/wanted to be opened to cost reduction will actually decrease. Although there is no hub opening cost in the current model, opening a hub may still be unnecessary in operational terms.

Comparing the scenarios with each other, cost reductions are clearly visible. But we need to examine what exactly the cost reductions in the entire scenario tell us. While preparing our freight transportation model using platooning, our goal is actually cost minimization. We minimize the cost, but we do not have the current scenario without platooning. In order to understand the effectiveness of platooning, the current scenario also needs to be analyzed. To do this, we modified our model. The only thing we did for this was to force the model to direct transportation. With a new constraint we added, we forced direct shipment between all origin destinations.

$$y_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in N, \forall j \in N$$

After we run the model with this constraint, our calculated cost for the current system is around 409 million Turkish liras. After calculating the current cost, we compared it with the costs of the scenarios in the model we created and the cost reduction percentages for each scenario were as shown in TABLE II.

These reductions have a cost saving of up to 19 percent. We conclude from the results that, on average, all scenarios have a gain of around 11 percent. If we express the 11 percent gain in different ways, it means a daily gain of approximately 40 million Turkish liras, which corresponds to a saving of approximately 1 million liters of diesel. When we consider all the trucks in the flow in one day, this means a gain of 21.76 liters of diesel per truck. From an environmental perspective, approximately 58 kg of CO₂ emissions are reduced per truck.

TABLE 2
PERCENT SAVINGS OF DIFFERENT HUB AND ALPHA SCENARIOS

Number of Hubs	a = 0.744(2 trucks)	a = 0.653(3 trucks)	a = 0.610(4 trucks)	Total Average
3 Hubs	3,32%	5,36%	6,45%	
4 Hubs	5,20%	8,28%	9,97%	
5 Hubs	6,55%	10,15%	12,10%	
6 Hubs	7,58%	11,66%	13,86%	
7 Hubs	8,68%	13,07%	15,48%	
8 Hubs	9,61%	14,46%	17,09%	
9 Hubs	10,16%	15,29%	18,09%	
10 Hubs	10,67%	15,98%	18,94%	
Averages	7,72%	11,78%	14,00%	11,17%

B. Model Development and Validation

While interpreting and analyzing the results of the model we created, we proceeded based on the total transportation cost that we set as an objective. After this, we decided to analyze the challenging points of the project in a more operational sense and its adaptability to real life. First, we decided to simulate the waiting times of trucks that set off from different origins and arrived at the same hub point while forming a convoy. While doing this analysis, we examined the worst cases.

During our meeting with TIRPORT, we could not obtain any data regarding the departure times of the trucks and we decided that the most reasonable and realistic approach was to determine the departure times by making a triangular distribution. We created the triangular distribution, thinking that trucks could set off randomly, but that this would be more intense towards noon hours. Our method in calculating waiting times is to calculate the arrival time of each truck to the first hub, list the arrival times of the trucks with the same destination hubs in ascending order, and then group them into two, three or four groups according to the scenario we will examine respectively. Since the maximum waiting time in the convoy for each convoy group is the waiting time of the earliest arriving truck in the convoy for the last arriving truck, we assumed the difference between the arrival times of the first and last arriving trucks as waiting time. Then, we prepared the simulation by integrating it into our model using Python.

Let's establish a simple logic regarding the worst cases mentioned above. If we compare our scenarios according to convoy lengths, the longer the convoy, the longer the waiting times because the first vehicle in the convoy will wait for more vehicles. Likewise, as the number of hubs we use in the model increases, the amount of flow carried by platooning will be divided more. Accordingly, the average flow amount between any two hubs will decrease as the number of hubs increases. We predict that decreasing flow amounts will reduce the frequency of convoys and cause an increase in waiting times. Therefore, we decided to conduct our analysis in a scenario with 10 hubs and 4 trucks in length, where we predicted that waiting times would be highest. In the worst case scenario, where the maximum convoy length is 4 in convoys between two hubs, the average waiting time for the first truck in the convoy to the last truck is 10,59 minutes on average. When we examined the waiting times in each convoy one by one, we noticed a few extreme waiting times that would seriously increase the average. In these specific cases, for example, instead of waiting for the 5th truck, it can be divided into two convoys in the form of 3-2, or instead of the first truck of a convoy waiting for the other trucks, where we predict that the waiting time will be high, it can be included in the previous convoy and a convoy of 5 trucks can be formed. If this is done, there will be a significant decrease in the average waiting time which we can disregard.

Another issue is empty mileage, which is when trucks return to the origin city they came from after carrying loads to the hubs, with empty loads. While the trucks leave their loads at the hubs, it is also possible that there are loads brought to that hub from another hub via platooning. Freights arriving at the hubs can also be transported to their destination

Figure 5: The Graph of Percent Savings to Alpha and Hub Scenarios

Again, as we saw and commented in the previous graph, as we increase the number of hubs, the increase in our savings percentage decreases.

points with trucks returning to the same point. Our empty mileage analysis here focuses on the worst case, as in waiting time, since in some cases there is a possibility that trucks will return empty after arriving at the hubs. As a worst case, we thought of an extreme scenario such as all the trucks coming to the hubs returning empty. On the other hand, when we make the worst case calculation, we need to consider the current system for comparison. Since TIRPORT's current system is focused on full truck load, empty mileage is not actually an issue. But as a reference, in our meeting with them, they suggested taking the empty mileage rate as 30%. When we simulated the empty mileages in our own model in Python, we saw that among our different hub and α scenarios, the empty mileage was at least approximately 1/3 of the current system.

C. Consideration of Alternatives

In the comprehensive analysis of alternative platooning applications, we discerned three discrete systems: Scheduled Platooning, Opportunistic Platooning, and Orchestrated Platooning. Opportunistic Platooning manifests as the spontaneous formation of platoons among trucks in close proximity, while Orchestrated Platooning entails centralized management by Platooning Service Providers (PSPs). In light of the persistent imperative for substantial infrastructure development to facilitate expansive business operations and accommodate spontaneous platoon formations, coupled with limited data provided by TIRPORT, our predilection converges towards the Scheduled Platooning system.

This proclivity emanates from the strategic alignment of the Scheduled Platooning alternative with our operational exigencies. Specifically, this system adeptly leverages premeditated travel information and platoon management, thereby engendering a structured and meticulously organized framework for platooning applications. The predilection for Scheduled Platooning is predicated upon its capacity to mitigate uncertainties and enhance the predictability of platoon logistics, thereby catering to the requisites of a sophisticated operational landscape. This preference is substantiated by the discerned harmony between the methodological precision afforded by Scheduled Platooning and the imperatives of our operational milieu. Additionally, we encountered various alternatives regarding potential hub selection. Our first alternative was to identify central points in the regions of Turkey and determine them as potential hubs, but we did not use this because not every central point was on roads suitable for platooning. Secondly, we thought of choosing hubs according to the flows of each city in Turkey, but the most appropriate method for choosing potential hubs was to proceed through roads suitable for platooning. That's why we took advantage of the existing motorway map in Turkey and determined the cities on it as potential hubs.

Finally, after creating our model, we examined the discount factor, or α , in our model in 3 different scenarios. These were the α values chosen based on the presence of 2, 3 and 4 trucks in convoy in the platooning system. As we stated in section 2.c, as a result of our research, we found the average α value to be 0.744 in the platooning system

containing 2 trucks, 0.653 in the platooning system containing 3 trucks, and 0.610 in the platooning system containing 4 trucks. According to the results, the most advantageous value seems to be the platooning system containing 4 trucks, because as the number of trucks in the convoy increases, air resistance decreases and thus fuel consumption decreases significantly. However, apart from the numerical results, the disadvantage is that as the number of trucks increases, it becomes practically difficult to create a platooning system. In terms of creating a platooning system with a length of 4 trucks in each convoy, it becomes unrealistic and almost impossible.

D. Solution Methodologies

a) *Collection and Analysis of Data for Existing Transportation Network:* This comprehensive examination encompasses various critical parameters, such as routes, flow amounts, speeds, distances, fuel consumption, emissions, and associated costs. To facilitate a thorough understanding of the current state of the transportation infrastructure, an attentive investigation into the geographic information system software is proposed. To determine the motorways and potential hub locations depending on these motorways, OpenStreetMap and ArcMap software have been used in this project.

b) *Developing a Model & Conducting Experiments:* The implementation of the model (see 4.1) was executed through the utilization of the Python programming language. Python was used as the main coding framework for creating and implementing the model because of its widespread adoption and large library ecosystem. In order to simulate the application of hub-based platooning technology in Turkey, the behavior and performance of convoys on selected routes were investigated. Under this review, different scenarios helped determine which cities could be designated as hubs.

c) *Comparing Hub and Truck Scenarios in Current System and Suggested New Motorway:* 24 distinct scenarios arise as if combining the scenarios of 3–10 hubs with 2, 3, and 4 trucks in both scenarios. These scenarios' cost amounts were evaluated. Based on the collected data, it was shown that the overall cost decreased with an increase in hub count. However, the cost increment eventually decreased as the number of hubs rose. There is a parallel situation with truck numbers. The new motorway opening scenario provides a significant total cost reduction for the same truck numbers.

E. Scenario and What-If Analysis

The most limiting situation in the current scenario is that we cannot choose our potential hubs from the east of

Figure 6: Map of Turkey with Future Gerede-Gürbulak Motorway

Turkey and the Black Sea region. The main reason for this is that there are no motorways we need for platooning in those regions. We know that the Karayolları Genel Müdürlüğü aims to increase Turkey's total motorway length in the long term. However, the Gerede-Gürbulak motorway project, which has news and speculation even though it has not become official yet, caught our attention (see Fig. 6). This motorway, starting from Bolu and extending to the Ağrı Gürbulak border gate, is an important project that can be an international logistics corridor. Therefore, in addition to the current system, we wanted to examine the difference that the scenario in which the Gerede-Gürbulak motorway would exist would affect our model and results, in the form of a What-If analysis

During integrating this new scenario into our model and code, the parts that required changes were our hub locations set and inter-hub distances. We made these changes and solve different α and different number of hub scenarios in our model.

TABLE 4
TOTAL COST AND PERCENTAGE REDUCTION OF FUTURE GEREDE-GÜRBUKAK MOTORWAY MODEL

Number of Hubs	$\alpha = 0.744(2 \text{ trucks})$	$\alpha = 0.653(3 \text{ trucks})$	$\alpha = 0.610(4 \text{ trucks})$	Total Average
3 hubs	₺ 396.620.678,00	₺ 388.966.148,00	₺ 384.965.574,00	
4 hubs	₺ 389.321.912,00	₺ 378.023.444,00	₺ 372.164.083,00	
5 hubs	₺ 383.386.301,00	₺ 368.911.283,00	₺ 361.434.275,00	
6 hubs	₺ 378.818.575,00	₺ 363.289.759,00	₺ 355.405.696,00	
7 hubs	₺ 374.837.653,00	₺ 358.237.330,00	₺ 349.723.725,00	
8 hubs	₺ 371.009.394,00	₺ 353.057.626,00	₺ 344.049.855,00	
9 hubs	₺ 367.362.049,00	₺ 348.278.434,00	₺ 338.542.412,00	
10 hubs	₺ 364.312.288,00	₺ 344.167.976,00	₺ 333.832.375,00	
	₺ 378.208.606,25	₺ 362.866.500,00	₺ 355.014.749,38	₺ 365.363.285,21

Number of Hubs	$\alpha = 0.744(2 \text{ trucks})$	$\alpha = 0.653(3 \text{ trucks})$	$\alpha = 0.610(4 \text{ trucks})$	Total Average
3 hubs	3,32%	5,36%	6,45%	
4 hubs	5,26%	8,41%	10,11%	
5 hubs	6,89%	11,08%	13,38%	
6 hubs	8,18%	12,80%	15,31%	
7 hubs	9,33%	14,39%	17,18%	
8 hubs	10,46%	16,07%	19,11%	
9 hubs	11,55%	17,67%	21,05%	
10 hubs	12,49%	19,07%	22,76%	
	8,43%	13,11%	15,67%	12,40%

Figure 7: The Graph of Total Costs to Alpha and Hub Scenarios with New Motorway

As can be seen in TABLE III, while the average profit percentage in the current model is 11.17, it rises to 12.40 here. And again, the profit from 21.76 liters per truck

increases to 23.80. Also, the plot of the current system's and What-if system's total costs can be seen in fig. 3.

The new motorway opening scenario provides a significant total cost reduction for the same α values shown in Fig. 7. There are similar gains in other numerical analyses. This numerical analysis actually shows us how much potential the Gerede-Gürbulak highway has and how cost minimization can be improved in this way.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The project delivers an integrated hub-based platooning system within Tirport's logistics operations. First of all, we identified and optimized platooning routes within the road transportation network, employing network optimization methods with hub-based methodology. As a result, there were concrete benefits such as reduced travel duration, reduced empty mileages, and cost savings. The implementation of platooning arcs in the road freight transportation network has resulted in a notable reduction in fuel consumption and accordingly a significant reduction in CO2 emission, in line with objectives for environmental sustainability. The widespread implementation of platooning technology has not only complied with safety rules but has also yielded comprehensive data-driven insights to enhance decision-making in the transportation network. The organization can successfully achieve significant cost reductions by reducing fuel consumption and empty mileages, thereby improving its overall profitability.

Integrating platooning technology into the current logistics and transportation infrastructure required guaranteeing compatibility with communication, navigation, and control systems. The identification of suitable hub centers strategically located for platooning has been a crucial achievement. The project predominantly employed Python as the programming language and ArcGIS Desktop for acquiring comprehensive data on highways and freight routes. The platooning model was created, executed, and confirmed through a sequence of trials and tests, taking into account several criteria such as platooning convoy size, or number of hubs. After concluding our model for choosing appropriate hubs for platooning, we upgraded our model for the operational phase which included the incorporation of waiting times of trucks for each other when combining a convoy in a hub and the calculation of empty mileages. According to our upgraded model, we discovered that the waiting times are negligible and even in the worst case, there is a reduction in total empty mileage.

The implemented model utilizes advanced algorithms for hub decisions and platooning decisions to optimize the load flows through motorways in Turkey. This integrated approach has contributed to the effectiveness of the transportation network. Future plans for Tirport can cover the initiative plans to further improve and extend the routes used for platooning within Turkey's transportation network. The emphasis will be on incorporating innovative technology and innovations that improve the effectiveness and security of platooning operations. In other words, they can work on the infrastructure of Turkey's motorway to integrate the platooning systems for trucks with a safety prioritization. Continuous communication with relevant parties and

ongoing analysis of data will be crucial for improving the platooning model and adjusting to changing transportation requirements. The project's objective is to remain up-to-date with regulatory breakthroughs in platooning technology and to predict prospective obstacles or advancements in the field. Since one of the objectives was to reduce the fuel consumption and CO2 emissions to the environment, Tırport can also consider adding the existing railroad networks into the transportation equation to further optimize the system. The efficient incorporation of platooning technology into the current logistics and transportation infrastructure represents a significant accomplishment.

The implementation of platooning technology can have a profound effect on the organization. The optimized platooning routes have led to a potential of significant reductions in transportation time, costs, emissions, and empty mileages. Also, the enhanced traffic flow and safety may contribute to a more efficient logistics network. Therefore, the company may achieve substantial financial savings by reducing fuel use and operational expenses. Furthermore, the adoption of platooning technology may position the organization as an industry leader on platooning technology, embracing innovation and sustainability.

In a nutshell, the project has effectively achieved its objectives, demonstrated a beneficial influence on the organization and environment, and laid the groundwork for continuous enhancements and progress in platooning technology inside the road transportation network.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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VII. APPENDIX

C_i = coefficient of city i

$$C_i = \frac{\text{Number of organized industrial zone on city } i}{\text{Total number of organized industrial zone in Turkey}} + \frac{\text{The outflow of city } i}{\text{Total outflow of Turkey}} + \frac{\text{Population of city } i}{\text{Total population of Turkey}}$$

(2.C.1)

Fig. 1. A Simple Flowchart of Our System

Fig 2. Map of Turkey's Motorway Network

```

def modeltry(file):
    cost = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 0)
    flow = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 4)
    flow2 = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 4)
    cost_interhub = pd.read_excel(file, sheet_name = 2)

    I=np.arange(1,82).tolist()
    J=np.arange(1,82).tolist()
    K = [1, 6, 9, 10, 14, 16, 17, 20, 22, 27, 33, 34, 35, 39, 40, 41, 45, 51, 54, 59, 68, 77, 80, 81]
    L = [1, 6, 9, 10, 14, 16, 17, 20, 22, 27, 33, 34, 35, 39, 40, 41, 45, 51, 54, 59, 68, 77, 80, 81]
    Q = 10 # desired number of hub
    alpha = 0.744

    Routes=[(i,j,k,l) for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L]
    DirectAssignment=[(i,j) for i in I for j in J]

    flow = dict(((i,j,k,l),flow[j][i]) for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L)
    fuelcost = dict(((i,j),cost[j][i]) for i in I for j in J)
    flowdirect = dict(((i,j),flow2[j][i]) for i in I for j in J)
    fuelcostinterhub = dict(((k,l),cost[l][k]) for k in K for l in L)

    HubRouteCost=dict(((i,j,k,l),(flow[i,j,k,l])*(fuelcost[i,k]+ alpha*fuelcostinterhub[k,l]+ fuelcost[l,j]))
    for i in I for j in J for k in K for l in L)
    DirectRouteCost= dict(((i,j),(flowdirect[i,j])*(fuelcost[i,j]))
    for i in I for j in J)

    m = gp.Model("cf1")
    m.ModelSense = GRB.MINIMIZE

    xk=m.addVars(K,name="City Nodes",vtype=GRB.BINARY,obj=0)
    yijk1=m.addVars(Routes,name="Hub Used Routes",obj=HubRouteCost)
    yij=m.addVars(DirectAssignment,name="Direct Routes",obj=DirectRouteCost)

    desiredhub = m.addConstr((quicksum(xk[k]
    for k in K) <= Q), "Desired Hub")

    directorhub = m.addConstrs(( yij[i,j]+ quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l]
    for k in K for l in L) == 1
    for i in I for j in J), "Direct or Hub Decision Constraint")

    hub1 = m.addConstrs((quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l] for l in L) <= xk[k] for i in I for j in J for k in K), "Hub1")
    hub2 = m.addConstrs((quicksum(yijk1[i,j,k,l] for k in K) <= xk[l] for i in I for j in J for l in L), "Hub2")

    m.optimize()

    for v in m.getVars():
        if v.x > 0:
            print(f"{v.varName}: {v.x}")

    return(m.objVal)

modeltry("temporary data (1).xls")

```

Fig. 3. The Python Code of Our Model

Fig. 4. The Graph of Total Costs to Alpha and Hub Scenarios

Fig. 5. The Graph of Percent Savings to Alpha and Hub Scenarios

Fig. 6. The Turkey Map with Future Gerede-Gürbulak Motorway

Fig. 7. The Graph of Total Costs to Alpha and Hub Scenarios with New Motorway

TABLE I
TOTAL COSTS OF DIFFERENT HUB AND ALPHA SCENARIOS

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Number of Hubs	a = 0.744(2 trucks)	a = 0.653(3 trucks)	a = 0.610(4 trucks)	Total Average
2	3 Hubs	₺ 396.620.678,00	₺ 388.966.148,00	₺ 384.965.574,00	
3	4 Hubs	₺ 389.531.633,00	₺ 378.463.731,00	₺ 372.651.736,00	
4	5 Hubs	₺ 384.607.595,00	₺ 372.035.413,00	₺ 365.553.370,00	
5	6 Hubs	₺ 380.913.131,00	₺ 366.998.049,00	₺ 359.907.058,00	
6	7 Hubs	₺ 377.089.297,00	₺ 362.431.019,00	₺ 354.875.292,00	
7	8 Hubs	₺ 373.885.092,00	₺ 358.033.648,00	₺ 349.977.389,00	
8	9 Hubs	₺ 371.995.064,00	₺ 355.452.027,00	₺ 347.027.410,00	
9	10 Hubs	₺ 370.284.569,00	₺ 353.344.657,00	₺ 344.552.831,00	
10		₺ 380.615.882,38	₺ 366.965.586,50	₺ 359.938.832,50	₺ 369.173.433,79

TABLE II
PERCENT SAVINGS OF DIFFERENT HUB AND ALPHA SCENARIOS

Number of Hubs	a = 0.744(2 trucks)	a = 0.653(3 trucks)	a = 0.610(4 trucks)	Total Average
3 Hubs	3,32%	5,36%	6,45%	
4 Hubs	5,20%	8,28%	9,97%	
5 Hubs	6,55%	10,15%	12,10%	
6 Hubs	7,58%	11,66%	13,86%	
7 Hubs	8,68%	13,07%	15,48%	
8 Hubs	9,61%	14,46%	17,09%	
9 Hubs	10,16%	15,29%	18,09%	
10 Hubs	10,67%	15,98%	18,94%	
Averages	7,72%	11,78%	14,00%	11,17%

TABLE III
TOTAL COSTS AND PERCENTAGE REDUCTIONS OF FUTURE GEREDE-GÜRBULAK
MOTORWAY MODEL

Number of Hubs	a = 0.744(2 trucks)	a = 0.653(3 trucks)	a = 0.610(4 trucks)	Total Average
3 hubs	₺ 396.620.678,00	₺ 388.966.148,00	₺ 384.965.574,00	
4 hubs	₺ 389.321.912,00	₺ 378.023.444,00	₺ 372.164.083,00	
5 hubs	₺ 383.386.301,00	₺ 368.911.283,00	₺ 361.434.275,00	
6 hubs	₺ 378.818.575,00	₺ 363.289.759,00	₺ 355.405.696,00	
7 hubs	₺ 374.837.653,00	₺ 358.237.330,00	₺ 349.723.725,00	
8 hubs	₺ 371.009.394,00	₺ 353.057.626,00	₺ 344.049.855,00	
9 hubs	₺ 367.362.049,00	₺ 348.278.434,00	₺ 338.542.412,00	
10 hubs	₺ 364.312.288,00	₺ 344.167.976,00	₺ 333.832.375,00	
	₺ 378.208.606,25	₺ 362.866.500,00	₺ 355.014.749,38	₺ 365.363.285,21
Number of Hubs	a = 0.744(2 trucks)	a = 0.653(3 trucks)	a = 0.610(4 trucks)	Total Average
3 hubs	3,32%	5,36%	6,45%	
4 hubs	5,26%	8,41%	10,11%	
5 hubs	6,89%	11,08%	13,38%	
6 hubs	8,18%	12,80%	15,31%	
7 hubs	9,33%	14,39%	17,18%	
8 hubs	10,46%	16,07%	19,11%	
9 hubs	11,55%	17,67%	21,05%	
10 hubs	12,49%	19,07%	22,76%	
	8,43%	13,11%	15,67%	12,40%

C_i = coefficient of city i

$$C_i = \frac{\text{Number of organized industrial zone on city i}}{\text{Total number of organized industrial zone in Turkey}} + \frac{\text{The outflow of city i}}{\text{Total outflow of Turkey}} + \frac{\text{Population of city i}}{\text{Total population of Turkey}}$$

Equation 1: Coefficient Calculation (II.C)

C_{ij}^{km} = total cost of transportation from origin i to destination j going through hubs k and m , respectively. (per flow)

a = interhub discount factor

$$C_{ij}^{km} = C_{ik} + aC_{km} + C_{mj}$$

Equation 2: Cost Parameter Calculation (II.C)

T_s = travel cost without using platooning(traditional freight transportation)

s = travel cost per vehicle without platooning , n = number of trucks

$$T_s = s.n$$

T_p = travel cost with platooning

a = travel cost per vehicle with platooning(leading vehicle, manned)

b = travel cost per vehicle with platooning(following vehicle, unmanned)

$$T_p = a + (n-1)b$$

$$\alpha = \frac{T_p}{T_s} = \frac{a + (n-1)b}{sn}$$

Equation 3: α Factor Calculation (II.C)

TripChat: A Long-term Planning Agent Hierarchy for Travel

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Abstract— In this work, we introduce a zero-shot, unsupervised trip and travel planner. Planning a trip automatically has several use cases - it can save people time and money, help people create better itineraries, and provide inspiration. Our framework uses a hierarchical multi-agent approach to coordinate, gather real-world data using APIs, and plan out a travel plan. Existing AI-based approaches for travel planning are often too simplistic and inflexible, rely on outdated data, or are of poor quality and detail. Our results show that our output plans generated this way are comparable to the best human made plans, approaching similar levels of detail, experiences, and personalization.

Keywords—Artificial intelligence (AI), Function calling, Large language models, Machine Learning (ML), Multi-agent hierarchy

I. INTRODUCTION

A fundamental difficulty for travellers in the modern era of travel is the lack of a centralized, real-time system that provides individualized suggestions. This gap in the travel planning process is multifaceted, encompassing aspects such as local events, flight bookings, car rentals, cultural insights, and weather updates. The complexity of planning trips, especially those involving multiple destinations or activities, further worsens the issue. A solution is needed not only to improve the trip experience but also to streamline the decision-making process, therefore lowering the time and effort engaged in travel preparation. This need becomes more pronounced when considering the dynamic nature of travellers' preferences and real-world availability, requiring the system to be robust against these changes. To address this challenge, we introduce TripChat, a novel solution designed to generate efficient and tailored travel plans. TripChat leverages a hierarchical agent structure implemented with Microsoft's Autogen [4] framework for multi-agent systems. This structure allows for specialized agents, each with distinct responsibilities, to collaboratively create comprehensive travel plans. The system's architecture is built on the principles of intelligent route modification, comprehensive planning, and real-time adaptability. It can complete a wide range of travel requests, from simple day trips to complex multi-stop excursions. An entire trip plan is generated in under 4 minutes. Our code can be found here: <https://github.com/xTRam1/TripChat>

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Agent Hierarchy

We designed a hierarchical agent structure where agents of different responsibilities work together for the common goal of creating a trip plan. In other words, the tasks of finding local events, hotels, flights, etc. are abstracted out into different teams and agents. For this, we use Microsoft's Autogen [4] framework for multi-agent systems. We use its GroupChat framework, which enables the agents in a system to talk with each other for collaboration. A GroupChat works in "rounds."

Figure 1: A Diagram of the Agent Hierarchy

In each round, the group chat manager selects a speaker to talk and contribute to the conversation, according to the past chat memory, the user query, and its reasoning capabilities. In our implementation, we gave the agents themselves the ability to "suggest" the next speaker to talk to create a hierarchy structure.

This hierarchy structure can be found in Fig. 1.

All the agent system prompts are designed so that everyone is aware of its team members' capabilities and who they are allowed to talk to. We implemented this kind of structure by using the "function-calling" capabilities of

LLMs: In reality, only low-level agents actually call the tools that interact with the outside world (such as interacting with the web, with travel APIs like booking.com search, and Wikipedia); whereas, the “functions” of the team members are functions that used for calling these low-level agents. The low-level agents are implemented with the Langchain framework. For a more detailed description of how a group chat proceeds, please see the Group Chat Implementation section.

B. Why Hierarchy

Continuing from the previous description of our hierarchical agent structure, we now delve into the rationale behind choosing a multi-agent setup instead of a single agent with access to all APIs. This decision is driven primarily by considerations of scalability and context length management. In a single-agent framework with access to a wide array of functions, the agent’s capacity to effectively select and utilize the appropriate functions and arguments diminishes as the number of available functions increases. This is particularly evident in complex scenarios involving a multitude of potential actions and choices. Such an overload leads to drastic inaccuracies in function name selection and argument formulation. By contrast, our multi-agent architecture ensures that each agent has access only to a specific subset of functions relevant to their designated role. This targeted access significantly enhances the precision of function calling, as each agent specializes in a particular domain, ensuring more accurate and contextually appropriate function and argument selections. Another critical aspect is the management of context length in chat-based interactions. In a single-agent system tasked with handling an entire trip-planning conversation, the necessity to retain all context within the agent’s limited memory poses a great challenge: As trip plans become more intricate, it becomes infeasible to fit the entire chat history within the model’s context length. This limitation often leads to suboptimal results, as the agent might either forget previous parts of the conversation or make poor judgments due to incomplete context. Methods like context summarization, while useful, tend to be lossy and exacerbate these issues as the conversation extends. Our hierarchical multi-agent structure effectively addresses this challenge. In this setup, lower-level details are only retained within the context of subordinate agents, while higher-level agents in the hierarchy are not burdened with these granular detail: Instead, they receive summarized reports from the lower levels. This approach not only keeps the context length manageable, even in extended conversations but also optimizes the use of the model provider’s API. Since we do not need to include every detail of the trip history in API calls, the queries become more focused and cost-effective. In summary, our decision to employ a hierarchical multi-agent system is a strategic choice to enhance scalability, function calling accuracy, and effective context length management. This architecture ensures that our system remains robust, efficient, and capable of handling complex trip-planning tasks with a high degree of precision and user satisfaction.

C. Group Chat Implementation

The group chat starts with the group chat manager coordinating a chat with the system prompt: “Hey everyone cooperate and help Agent Brain in his task of generating a good trip plan.” When the user submits their query, the brain takes the user’s query and initiates a chat with the group chat

manager by passing in the query as the first message in the group chat. Hence, the groupchat manager starts this round-based chat and selects one agent to speak in each round. For this, we defined a custom speaker selection logic so that the group chat manager is allowed to select only the team leaders to speak, and team leaders themselves suggest their most relevant team members to speak by appending an uppercase “NEXT:” message at the end. Every round, the group chat manager makes a decision based on the suggested next speaker by the previous agent and the overall all conversation history to select the next speaker. Thus, teams only talk within themselves. After their team-internal discussion ends, team leaders report back to the group chat manager, and a new team leader is selected to speak, and so on. During this discussion, team members are allowed to call the low-level agents (websearch, booking.com API etc.) for “help” before reporting back. Except termination user proxy, no agent has to ability to terminate the group chat. After each team’s discussion ends and the group chat manager is satisfied, the manager selects brain to speak which asks the user if they are satisfied with the answer. If they are, the group chat manager selects the termination user proxy to speak whose whole purpose is to terminate the conversation and return to the user.

```

    "You are team member TouristicAttractionFinder. You know about touristic
    attractions and can provide "
    "information about them. You MUST only use the tools provided to you "
    "with inputs relating to tourist attractions and nothing else."
    " You MUST first use webSearch, after executing the webSearch, you must
    call update_travel_plan to update your section
    (EventPlanning.TouristicAttractionFinder) with event in the format:"
    """
    {
      "TouristicAttractions": {
        "Attraction1": {
          "Name": "",
          "Description": "",
          "OpeningHours": "",
          "EntryFee": ""
          // Additional attractions can be added in a similar format
        }
      }
    },"""
    "You MUST end your message with 'NEXT: HeadofEventPlanning' and report
    back your results."
  
```

Figure 2: An Example System Prompt for A Single Agent, TouristicAttractionFinder

D. Shared Object

The entire group chat serves to populate a shared JSON object (so every agent has access to update, delete, and add information to this object). In the system prompts of team members, they are given the section they are responsible for updating in the shared object. For instance, TouristicAttractionFinder agent has the system prompt displayed in Fig. 2.

Each team member has similar system prompts. They have two designated functions; one for updating the shared object, and another for using other tools (such as web search, booking API, etc) When their team leaders suggest them to the speaker, in their turn, team members take the relevant information and call their low-level agent to access real-time information. Then, they call the update_travel_plan function. This function takes the section to be updated, and the data to

insert (a JSON object as well). Finally, the team member updates the shared object with this function, shares the findings in the group chat and reports back to the team leader. Since each agent has assigned sections in this object, our solution is similar to multiple people updating a shared Google Doc with different access rights. So our idea of collaborating to create a common final product is applicable to any domain that has similar problems.

III. EVALUATION

Our evaluation uses an Alpaca Farm [2] style LLM judge for scaling and consistency with planning agent evaluations. Furthermore, since travel planning metrics have not been established in the research literature, we develop five categories for travel planning evaluation using a compilation of 20+ travel itineraries and checklists.

TABLE I
EVALUATION RESULTS USING OUR JUDGE LLM

Category	Human Travel Plan	TripChat Travel Plan
Destination Accuracy	99%	88%
Travel Event Personalization	99%	77%
Budget Management and Value Alignment	99%	88%
Logistical Coherence and Convenience	88%	55%
Cultural Engagement and Experiential Richness	99%	88%
Non-hallucinatory	100%	99%

The evaluation metrics were meticulously designed to address each aspect of travel planning. First, the Destination Accuracy metric ensures the selected location resonates with the traveler’s interests, be it cultural immersion, adventure, or relaxation, forming the foundational element of the travel experience. Following this, Travel Event Personalization Alignment scrutinizes the itinerary’s customization to the traveler’s unique preferences, enhancing their overall experience by personalizing activities and events. In practicality, Budget Management and Value Alignment examines how the plan aligns with financial constraints while maximizing experience value, striking a crucial balance between affordability and quality. Logistical Coherence and Convenience then evaluate the arrangement’s practicality, focusing on transportation, accommodation, and the logical sequencing of activities for a seamless and stress-free journey. Lastly, Cultural Engagement and Experiential Richness delves into the depth of cultural immersion and learning opportunities, enriching the traveler’s connection with the destination. Collectively, these categories form a robust and holistic framework, ensuring each travel plan is comprehensively assessed from multiple critical dimensions. We have developed a comprehensive evaluation system for AI-generated travel plans by utilizing GPT-4 as the LLM judge

across the five established categories. In order to compare the quality of our generated plans, we compare our plans to a set of 11 baseline plans manually curated by hand to maximize aspects of our 5 evaluation criteria. We then use the same LLM judge to evaluate our generated plans on the same metric, and then compare them. Initially, we encountered issues with the LLM being inconsistent with its evaluation on the manually curated baseline plans. However, we were able to make our judge much more consistent and accurate by using 2 different techniques for language model prompting: chain-of-thought prompting [3] and using in-context examples [1]. We used around 10 in context examples, with one positive and one negative example for each criteria. We used chain-of-thought for each in context example to allow the judge to understand why they should come to that conclusion. Our findings show that TripChat is almost as good as our manually curated human travel plan, with results shown in Fig. 3

IV. CONCLUSION

We show that TripChat can serve as a first step towards an automated trip planner, which can either be used by individuals or by travel agencies to save time and money. TripChat is novel because it demonstrates the ability to plan using real-world data, which also drastically reduces hallucinatory outputs. Moreover, the hierarchical multi-agent structure ensures that AI maintains a coherent and reliable line of reasoning throughout the planning process, aligning closely with the expert-level plans in our evaluations. As for future work, teams or agents whose tasks and results do not depend on each other can work in parallel to make the trip-planning process even faster and more efficient.

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Image-Guided Object Detection using OWL-ViT and Enhanced Query Embedding Extraction

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Abstract—Computer vision has been receiving increasing attention with the recent complex Generative AI models released by tech industry giants, such as OpenAI and Google. However, there is a specific subfield that we wanted to focus on, that is, Image-Guided Object Detection. A detailed literature survey directed us towards a successful study called Simple Open-Vocabulary Object Detection with Vision Transformers (OWL-ViT) [1], which is a multifunctional complex model that can also perform image-guided object detection as a side function. In this study, some experiments have been conducted utilizing OWL-ViT architecture as the base model and manipulated the necessary parts to achieve a better one-shot performance. Code and models are available on GitHub²

Keywords— Computer Vision, Open-Vocabulary Object Detection with Vision Transformers (OWL-ViT), Object Detection, Vision Transformers, End-to-End Training, Generalized Intersection over Union (gIoU) Loss, Mean Absolute (L1) Loss, CLIP, DETR, Cosine Similarity, Yolov8, MS-COCO Dataset

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there have been numerous developments in the use of artificial neural networks, which have expanded the areas of study for Artificial Intelligence. Especially in computer vision, a rapid increase has occurred in a number of distinct real-life applications since researchers discovered a huge range of new utilization areas for complex computer vision models.

These applications include segmentation and object detection. As they constantly work to improve the functionality of these models, some of them now accept multimodal queries such as markers and/or points, masks, and texts. For instance, a new model called Segment Anything (SAM) [2] was developed by Meta-AI to undergo this kind of multi-functionality. These improvements had a significant positive effect on the capability of zero-shot learning in computer vision models. Zero-shot learning is, as the name states, the model's ability to predict unseen data samples. In other words, it shows how generalizable the model is to its problem definition. This term has been used in many studies.

²https://github.com/melihserin/OWL-ViT_with_enhanced_query_embedding_network

After a detailed literature survey, some studies similar to this one are found. One of them is Simple Open-Vocabulary Object Detection with Vision Transformers (OWL-ViT) [1]. In OWL-ViT, they designed an open-vocabulary object detection method based only on transformer encoders (without any decoders). The model's pre-training process is similar to that of CLIP [3] training, which is essentially contrastive image-text pre-training on image-text representations. They then performed end-to-end training that was almost equivalent to DETR [4]. The model is agnostic to the source of the query representations because the image and text components of the model are not fused. Utilizing this aspect, they also used the model for one-shot image-conditioned object detection, which detects certain objects in an image using image query embeddings.

In this study, the aim is to train a model that can detect specific objects in an image defined by image queries that are not of categories fed into the model during training. A model is desired such that it is as generalizable as possible, which means that the model should detect objects not previously seen. To achieve this, several experiments are conducted using the OWL-ViT as the base model.

II. BACKGROUND

A. DETR [4]

Detection Transformers (DETR) presented a new method that considers object detection as a direct set prediction problem. The approach streamlines the detection pipeline, effectively removing the need for many hand-designed components, such as a non-maximum suppression procedure or anchor generation, that explicitly encode our prior knowledge about the task. The main components of the new framework are a set-based global loss that forces unique predictions via bipartite matching and a transformer encoder-decoder architecture. Given a fixed small set of learned object queries, DETR explains the relations between the objects and the global image context to directly output the final set of predictions in parallel. This model is conceptually simple and does not require a specialized library, unlike many other modern detectors. DETR demonstrates accuracy and run-time performance on par with the well-established and highly optimized Faster R-CNN [5] baseline on the challenging COCO [6] object detection dataset.

Fig. 1: Architecture of OWL-ViT for Image-Guided Object Detection

B. CLIP [3]

CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training) is pre-trained to predict if an image and a text snippet are paired together in its dataset. For each dataset, the names of all classes in the dataset were used as the set of potential text pairings and predicted the most probable (image, text) pair.

The image encoder inside the model is a computer vision backbone that computes a feature representation for the image, and the text encoder is a hypernetwork that generates the weights of a linear classifier based on the text specifying the visual concepts represented by the classes.

Fig. 2: Architecture of ViT

C. Vision Transformers [7]

While the Transformer [8] architecture has become the de facto standard for natural language processing tasks, its appli-

cations to computer vision remain limited. In vision, attention is either applied in conjunction with convolutional networks, or used to replace certain components of convolutional networks while maintaining their overall structure in place. We show that this reliance on CNNs [9] is not necessary, and that a pure transformer applied directly to sequences of image patches can perform very well on image classification tasks as in Figure 2 [10]. When pre-trained on large amounts of data and transferred to multiple mid-sized or small image recognition benchmarks (ImageNet [11], CIFAR-100 [12], VTAB [13], etc.), the ViT attains excellent results compared to state-of-the-art convolutional networks and requires substantially fewer computational resources to train.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective is to study visual query encoding for deep-object detection models. Nowadays, computer vision models accept multimodal queries, such as images, text, and/or markers, to perform tasks, such as segmentation, as in the case of SAM. In this study, we aim to explore the possibility of training an object detection model with visual queries to train not only the object search/detect module but also the semantic query encoding layers. OWL-ViT is used as the base model to train a one-shot image-guided object detection model on the customized datasets.

A. Model Architecture

In the architecture of OWL-ViT, two fundamental parts undergo the same procedure. These parts extract query and image

Fig. 3: Proposed Query Embedding Extraction

TABLE I: Customized Datasets used in this study.

Name	Train	Seen Test	Unseen Test	Categories
Digit Detection	280	120	30	10
Object Detection	400	100	25	5

embeddings from the query and target images successively.

To extract query embeddings, a vision transformer is used to obtain the feature vectors (tokens). The tokens contain the information for each image patch. These tokens are then fed into three different processes. First, by linearly projecting tokens onto the embedding dimension, class-embedding vectors for each patch are obtained. Consecutively, tokens go through two different Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) [14]. While one calculates a score showing the probability that each token is an object (objectness score), the other finds the corresponding bounding box coordinates for each token. A bias is added to the state location of each patch for the second MLP to return meaningful location coordinates. Finally, the top k class embeddings were chosen based on their objectness scores and used as query embeddings for the target image.

In the other part, the target image passes through the same pre-trained vision transformer. After the composition of image feature vectors, tokens are fed only into the linear projection layer and coordinate calculating MLP because we want to select the necessary image embeddings based on their similarity to query embeddings, not on objectness scores. To match the image and query embeddings, Cosine Similarity is used to obtain output logit scores for each image embedding. Subsequently, the output object(s) are defined as those with the highest scores.

Although the architecture of OWL-ViT is conceptually simple, it may lead to an overkill if the objective is object detection with image queries because the image queries are allowed to be small in size and chosen as basic as possible in order them to visually represent the corresponding object in a better way. Therefore, in one of the experiments, the part where the extraction of query embeddings occurs, is simplified to output only one representative embedding from the object query. This experiment uses a CNN network that is analogous to the one in [15] and has been pre-trained to

get a representative embedding for each object query image. Further information about this network is provided in the Model Details section.

B. Training

The OWL-ViT method involves a contrastive pre-training of images and texts, which is accomplished using Vision Transformers (ViT) with Multihead Attention Pooling (MAP) [16]. In this work, we made use of one of the pre-trained OWL-ViT models.

To ensure good performance, a series of training experiments are conducted with parameters close to those reported in the OWL-ViT paper. As the focus of this study is not on the object classification component, the loss used is tailored so that only the object detection function is optimized, for which the bipartite matching loss of DETR was employed with the necessary task-specific normalizations.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Model Details

ViT's working process begins with a given image being divided into many patches, the size of which is specified by the ViT-B/32 model. To suit this model, the input image must first be preprocessed. Assuming we have a 650x900 image, it must be resized to 768x768 pixels. The encoder then divides this image into 576 patches of 32x32, with each patch's feature representation vector (token) being of size 1x1x1024.

The query image is run through three processes - a linear projection layer to create embeddings of size 1x1x512, a MLP for objectness score and another MLP to return the bounding box coordinates for each token. For the bounding box MLP, center location information of each patch is fed into the MLP as biases to get more accurate bounding boxes. In this case, as the query image contains one object only, the objectness score

TABLE II: AP50 Performance of Image-Conditioned Detection Models

Object Detection		
Method	Seen Test	Unseen Test
OWL-ViT(ViT-B/32)	73.5	58.3
OWL-ViT(ViT-B/32)(ours)	86.2	80.0
OWL-ViT+CNN(ours)	79.5	68.2
Digit Detection		
OWL-ViT(ViT-B/32)	10.8	19.2
OWL-ViT(ViT-B/32)(ours)	19.6	15.0
OWL-ViT+CNN(ours)	13.5	20.0

MLP is omitted and the embedding with the biggest bounding box is chosen as the query embedding.

The target image is also put through the linear projection layer and the MLP for box coordinates. As in Equation 1 [17], the Cosine Similarity is then used to compare the target image embeddings to the query embedding and the highest scoring bounding box is the output object in the target image. Target and query image embeddings are expressed as A and B, successively.

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\sum_i^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_i^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_i^n B_i^2}} \quad (1)$$

Moreover, in order to prevent an overabundance of query embedding extraction, it was opted to utilize a pre-trained CNN Network architecture which only works on one patch at a time instead of 576 different patches just like in Figure 3. One embedding that is created to describe an entire digit or another kind of object query image is generated by this process. The embedding is pre-trained on digit and object detection query images independently for approximately 50 epochs.

B. Dataset

In order to carry out this study, we generated two datasets tailored for this purpose. It should be noted that the pre-trained model applied as the base model was pre-trained on the LiT [18], O365 [19], and VG [20] datasets.

The first dataset was intended for digit detection and consisted of 10 labeled door number images and five digit images for each digit class, with classes 1 and 9 only used in the test set. The training set was composed of 280 pairs of target images and objects, with the test set on seen classes being 120 pairs and test set on unseen classes being 30 pairs as shown in the Table I.

The other dataset contained some of the MS-COCO classes, such as Horse, Car, Person, Airplane, and Elephant, with Elephant chosen as the unseen object class. There were five labeled target images and objects for each class, making the training set 400 pairs and unseen and seen test sets 25 and 100 pairs respectively as shown in the Table I.

Additionally, target images in the customized MS-COCO dataset were labeled using Yolov8 [21], a model that is successful for object detection.

C. Hyperparameters

Hyperparameter settings used in this study are as following

- Learning rate = 10^{-6}
- Weight Decay = 10^{-4}
- Equal weights for bounding box and gIoU losses

D. Loss

The bipartite matching loss introduced by the DETR is used, which is composed of L1 loss and gIoU loss. As in Equation 2 [22], the L1 loss is utilized to reduce the discrepancy between the target and the predicted bounding box by summing up all the absolute differences. To compute the Generalized Intersection over Union, two boxes A and B are firstly enclosed in the smallest convex shape C in S in R^n . As in Equation 3 [23], the ratio of C excluding A and B is then divided by the area of C.

$$L1 = \sum_i^n |y_{true} - y_{predicted}| \quad (2)$$

$$gIoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} - \frac{|C \setminus (A \cup B)|}{|C|} \quad (3)$$

E. Model Performances

As described above, the purpose is to identify corresponding objects in a target image to a query image. Table I shows the distribution of our custom datasets that contain target and query images as pairs. Evaluation is done with the AP50 metric as they did it in [1] and [24]. To compare our results, the results of the pre-trained model we used are also presented in Table II. The train and test losses are shown in Figure 4. Both Digit and Object Detection results clearly demonstrate the improvement of the performance of our image-guided object detection model on both seen and unseen test sets. Additionally, as seen in Table II, the OWL-ViT+CNN model has an edge when tested with unseen categories after it has been trained on the Digit Detection dataset. In contrast, the original OWL-ViT model is more adept at working with the COCO categories in the Object Detection dataset.

V. DISCUSSION

The primary obstacle we face is technical in nature. Developing intricate models necessitates GPUs and improved computers, which we don't have access to. We have been utilizing Google Colab during our work, though it is not the pro version so it has its own restrictions. We did our best to tackle this difficulty.

A. *Social, Environmental and Economic Impact*

We hope that this study is a positive step towards achieving one-shot image-guided object detection.

B. *Cost Analysis*

For the project, the duration and probable expenses for an online processor were essential.

C. *Standards*

The project will be held with special emphasis to IEEE, IET, EU and Turkish standards. Engineering code of conduct will be followed.

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, we employed OWL-ViT as the basis to construct a model of image-aided object detection which is also capable of detecting objects it has not encountered yet. Several experiments were conducted in which certain modifications were made to the original OWL-ViT model design to boost its performance. Based on the results, we are confident that we have taken a significant step forward.

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APPENDIX

A. Losses

Train and Test Loss of OWL-ViT on COCO Objects Dataset

OWL-ViT on Object Detection Dataset

Train and Test Loss of OWL-ViT+CNN on COCO Objects Dataset

OWL-ViT+CNN on Object Detection Dataset

Train and Test Loss of OWL-ViT on Digit Dataset

OWL-ViT on Digit Detection Dataset

Train and Test Loss of OWL-ViT+CNN on Digit Dataset

OWL-ViT+CNN on Digit Detection Dataset

Fig. 4: Losses

B. Qualitative Examples

The figures below shows query object images on the right while target images are situated on the left.

Fig. 5: Previously Seen Query Examples for Object Detection

Fig. 6: Unseen Query Example for Object Detection

Fig. 7: Previously Seen Query Examples for Digit Detection

Fig. 8: Unseen Query Example for Digit Detection

C. Failures

Fig. 9: Previously Seen Query Failures

Fig. 10: Unseen Query Failures

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KUUJE HIGHLIGHTS

Material Science and Artificial Intelligence: Insights from Professor Demircan Canadınc

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Abstract— In this interview, Professor Demircan Canadınc of Koç University explains his work at the intersection of material science and artificial intelligence (AI). Professor Canadınc has concentrated on the deformation of metallic substances as his area of expertise in the area of mechanics of materials. His current research, in collaboration with important institutions like Los Alamos National Laboratory, transforms the design of high-strength, smart shape memory alloys, and biomedically compatible metallic materials. His work addresses the challenges of creating alloys with a Young's modulus akin to human bone for orthopedic implants. Professor Canadınc uses AI to optimize the alloy composition with exceptional speed and efficiency which is a breakthrough that significantly improves upon the traditional, decades-long trial-and-error cycle in material design. This interview with Professor Canadınc explores the utilization of state-of-the-art techniques such as SEM and XPES housed in KUTTAM (Koç University Research Center for Translational Medicine) laboratory for the characterization of newly minted alloys. Professor Canadınc also sheds light on the broader usage of AI in materials science and his anticipation for the future applications of AI in the field.

Keywords—artificial intelligence in alloy design, deformation of metallic materials, material science, mechanical engineering, shape memory alloys

I. INTRODUCTION

Professor Demircan Canadınc is a material scientist and a professor at Koç University in the Department of Mechanical Engineering. By training, he is a mechanical engineer, as he has acquired all his degrees in mechanical engineering. In his research, his focus lies in the mechanics of materials.

He specializes in the deformation of metallic materials, specifically high-strength materials - shape memory alloys that are a class of the so-called smart materials - and biomedical metallic materials, such as implant materials. Professor Canadınc focuses on the design of their microstructures, compositions, and response to the mechanical loading under both monotonic and cyclic loading that is the fatigue behavior or, in other words, long-term behavior. Lately, he has been designing alloys using artificial intelligence.

"I took an introductory materials science course as an undergraduate student. After that, I was hooked!"

His journey with material science started back when he was an undergraduate student. The material response and metals attracted his attention. For that reason, he wanted to get involved in the solution of material problems, especially those concerning metals.

II. CURRENT RESEARCH

Professor Canadınc is involved in a few research areas that are important in many applications, including biomedical applications. In collaboration with Los Alamos National Laboratory in the United States, his research team designed new metallic materials using artificial intelligence that would exhibit high strength at elevated temperatures while also maintaining formability at low temperatures. In collaboration with his graduate students, he also addressed the problem of designing a biocompatible metallic implant material for orthopedic implants, ensuring that the mechanical biocompatibility is also satisfied. As bone has a very low elastic modulus and metals have much higher values than that, they wanted to design a metallic material that is both strong, formable into the desired shape, and exhibits Young's modulus, a measure of elasticity commonly used in material science, that is as close as possible to that of the bone. They used artificial intelligence to come up with the chemical composition that would give the desired result (Process summarized in Figure 1). We had an opportunity to ask a few questions about the details of his research during our interview.

A. How is Artificial Intelligence Used in Your Research?

"Firstly, we run different machine learning algorithms with different mathematical linearities that go over data we collected through experiments and literature on similar materials - data reported on existing and known materials. Then we train the algorithms, compare their performance, and pick the best one upon testing. The training is done on 80% of the data, so the algorithms never see the other 20% of the data. Once we train them, meaning that once the algorithm learns the unseen relationships we cannot see with the human eye, it creates mathematical functions. Once the functions are done,

Figure 1 The Process of creating alloys using Artificial Intelligence. [1]

we test those functions on the other 20% that algorithms have never seen before and pick the best-performing algorithm. Finally, we make predictions with that algorithm to discover new alloys.”

“After the new alloys are discovered, the researchers choose some of them to be manufactured and tested in real life. Depending on the level of precision various companies can manufacture the alloys. Typically, for high-precision manufacturing, there are special companies that focus on manufacturing exactly what the customers want. For some of the articles, Professor and his group collaborated with the TUŞAS Engines Industry, a Turkish company specializing in jet engines, which can produce materials with high precision. However, if such collaborations are not available, there are companies outside from which they can order the material. Therefore, when designing a material numerically, researchers ask for a given composition and then either order the material from outside vendors or have collaborators produce it for them. After that, the process of characterizing the material begins.”

B. How are the Alloys Created by Artificial Intelligence Characterized?

“For characterization purposes, we use the facilities at KUTTAM (Koç University Research Center for Translational Medicine). In my lab, there are simple setups for biocompatibility testing of biomedical materials. With the help of these setups, we immerse the samples in fluids that simulate the body environment, such as artificial saliva and artificial blood. We then check if the designed material satisfies the basic biocompatibility criteria. If it passes, we then proceed to the next level. For the characterization of those fluids and the sample surfaces, we use KUTTAM facilities. We use equipment such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Figure 2), X-ray photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPES) for surface oxidation analysis, X-ray diffraction for examining the material phases and texture, and Field Emission Electron Microscopy (FEACM). Additionally, for compatibility analysis to determine the amount of ions in the simulation fluids, we use Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICPMS). These are different techniques that we use and all of them are available in KUTTAM, which is why we carry out our research mostly at Koç University.”

Figure 2: Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy in the KUTTAM laboratory at Koç University

C. How do You Decide Which Materials to Focus on Given the Abundance of Options?

“As engineers, when designing a material, we always need to make decisions. For instance, with implant materials or biocompatible alloys we need to make sure that all the constituent elements of the alloy are also biocompatible by themselves. For that reason, we have Titanium, Tantalum, and Zirconium in those alloys. We do not include Aluminum, as it can cause Alzheimer’s or other disorders. With that being said, the selection is not always AI-based or random, there are some engineering decisions in the first place.”

“Element-wise, we only use metals listed in the periodic table that are naturally occurring on Earth. Usually, these metals are found in the form of compounds, so we need to separate them and that is what makes the rare metals expensive. We usually use metal powder in order to create new alloys. In terms of powder, there is a process called the atomization process, which allows the making of powders of any metal. However, this process is very specialized, and atomizing is already expensive, and rare metals like titanium, tantalum, or polonium make the metal powders even more expensive.”

III. LIMITATIONS THAT MATERIAL SCIENCE IS FACING

In our world governed by the laws of capitalism and supply and demand, many less profitable industries are experiencing difficulties. Some branches of scientific research are unfortunately considered to be less useful by society. Hence many researchers are facing various problems during their careers. We asked Prof. Demircan to tell us about some limitations he is facing throughout his research.

“Limitations in my field are mostly related to finances. Characterization equipment is very expensive, which is why we use a centralized laboratory here. Additionally, the cost of metal powders is rising as they are getting rare, and high-performance metals and alloys usually require the utility of some of those rare metals. Experimentation costs are high as well. Moreover, you need to have people willing to do research in the metallurgy field. These days, interest is mostly in computer science and while combining those two fields, as I do, can help, human interest remains an issue. When it comes to implant materials research, certain regulations are coming from such organizations as FDA in the United States, or Sağlık Bakanlığı (Ministry of Health) here in Turkey. Certain regulations need to be followed before testing on humans can proceed. Of course, they are actually needed, so I wouldn’t say it is a barrier, but it makes things go slow.”

IV. THE FUTURE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MATERIALS SCIENCE

Nowadays, the rapid advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) create a lot of change in many sectors and industries, from autonomous driving, and simple speech recognition to even manufacturing. Research and academia are no exception and neither is Material Science. AI has been increasingly utilized in material science to accelerate research, enhance understanding, and discover novel materials with desired properties.

A. What is Your Opinion on the Current Use of AI in Materials Science?

“Traditionally, using conventional metallurgic approaches to design a new class material, make trial and error, come up with a usable design and prove that it works, it takes between 10 to 30 years. However, when AI and existing data are used, it takes only around 6 to 12 months. Other researchers showed that the cost decreases by 90-95% due to the elimination of trial and error. Imagine a composition space as big as this office room, but target compositions are in the place of this bottle on the table. AI is directing you towards this bottle instead of going through all of the space experimentally. Of course, when the material is designed and manufactured, we need to conduct the experiments to validate our predictions, but we do not experiment with all possible compositions and that saves a lot of time.”

B. What about the Future of Materials Science? Does AI Have A Place in It?

“The future is as follows, but I am not sure when it is going to come. There will be problems and solutions to these problems will be detected by artificial intelligence. Given the duty, AI will decide itself on the solution method, come up with a prediction, make the alloy, test it, and then give us the solution. I think it will be implemented in the manufacturing processes in all the disciplines. But how long it will take - I don't know. However, at some point, it might change. This is the future aim, so how much of it will be accomplished or how much of it will be allowed by the society remains to be seen.”

"People like us will be mostly eliminated or maybe just directing the processes. But right now, it needs engineering decisions made by engineers."

V. PERSONAL ADVICE FROM PROFESSOR CANADIÇ

Falling in love with science, regardless of the type, is quite easy but deciding to become a scientist and to spend your life as a researcher, can be scary and overwhelming for some people, especially young and indecisive college students. Knowing that our audience is probably people who are interested in research, we decided to ask our interviewee a question that aims to give college students some direction.

A. What advice would you give to someone studying material science in terms of selecting areas of focus, considering the interdisciplinary nature of current problems?

“Well, this advice is valid for all the disciplines, but in the case of material science, it is an old field, not a new one. I would recommend learning the basics very well and then expanding the knowledge not only in the area of interest but also equipping themselves with additional tools such as

machine learning, chemical engineering, chemistry, medicine, or biology. That would definitely help with the interdisciplinary problems. I would recommend not being an expert on one thing only, but also expanding the knowledge in different directions, because many problems these days are interdisciplinary. I would try to focus on the intersection points of different disciplines with material science and then equip myself with the necessary tools depending on my interest. That is the advice that I would like to give.”

Many people consider research to be one of those industries that no one knows the details about because it is not as popularized as more common industries. We always hear the success stories but never the difficulties that the researchers are facing. The industry often seems to be impersonal. This can create a lot of uncertainty in the minds of aspiring scientists. To try and balance it out, we asked Professor Canadiç to tell us about the difficulties he personally faces as a material scientist in Turkiye.

“Everybody faces similar challenges, but there are also some personal ones. Some of these problems are related to Turkiye because the industry-academia relationship is not where it should be. This limits your ability to expand your horizons and reach out to the ones who can actually use your research outputs. Additionally, metallurgy is an old field - more than a century old - with its roots tracing back to the Stone Age, if we look at it practically. While it means that there is a lot of knowledge, it also means that there are many people in this field and the problems are not considered exciting anymore. This makes the research funding limited, as opposed to AI research in computer science, for instance. Carrying out research without proper funding becomes difficult.”

VI. CONCLUSION

In this interview, Professor Canadiç gave us a lot of insights about his research areas and the way the industry works in general. He touched upon the topics of the importance of Artificial Intelligence, and the potential future of material science. For our aspiring scientists, he also shared some advice and potential challenges that may be faced during the journey of becoming a researcher.

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We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our first guest professor who is featured in this journal, Professor Demircan Canadiç, for accepting our invitation, letting us conduct the interview, and showing us around the KUTTAM laboratory at Koç University. We are also thankful to the staff at KUTTAM for telling us about the various equipment and letting us take some pictures while we were there. We would like to say that this was an amazing experience for us and we learned a lot of things throughout this interview.

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